

Becoming a full professor in sociology/demography in France.

What explains the gender gap?

Angela Greulich*, Alain Chenu^S,

Yannick Savina[‡] and Jérôme Tourbeaux[‡]

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Abstract

This article examines whether, and to what extent, gender, meritocratic factors, and non-meritocratic mechanisms shape the transition to full professorship in sociology and demography in France. We draw on a unique longitudinal dataset covering the complete population of individuals who were recruited as assistant professors (“*maîtres de conférences*”) in sociology/demography (CNU section 19) at French universities between years 2000 and 2020s and follow their careers through 2021. Combining non-anonymous administrative records from the French Ministry of Higher Education and Research (MESRI) with manually coded information on publications, administrative responsibilities, awards, and institutional location, the dataset includes 658 individuals and allows for a detailed reconstruction of academic career trajectories. Using event history models, we estimate unconditional and conditional hazards of promotion to full professor, distinguishing between successive stages of the promotion process, including applications for qualification and for professorship positions. This approach makes it possible to identify how gender differences emerge across stages and to assess the contribution of each stage to the overall gender gap. We test a range of meritocratic explanations based on human and symbolic capital, such as publication quantity and quality, academic awards, and administrative experience, alongside non-meritocratic factors related to institutional prestige, geographic location, and mobility. Our results show that the gender gap in promotion to full professorship is substantial and arises primarily before candidates enter competition, with women being significantly less likely than men to apply for qualification, even at comparable levels of productivity. While differences in scientific production explain a large share of this gap, a non-negligible portion remains unexplained, pointing to gendered constraints related to mobility, costs of qualification, and self-selection. Moreover, persistent gender disparities at the final recruitment stage, particularly for external positions, suggest that discriminatory mechanisms in professorial hiring cannot be completely ruled out.

Keywords:

academic careers, tenure, human capital, social capital, gender, discrimination

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*Sciences Po, CRIS, Paris, France & Institut Universitaire de France. Corresponding author:
angela.greulich@sciencespo.fr

[§] Sciences Po, CRIS, Paris, France.

[£] Sciences Po, CRIS, Paris, France.

^μ IGESR, Ministère d'éducation, du sport et de la recherche, Paris, France

1. Introduction

In this article, we test whether, and to what extent, gender and meritocratic as well as other non-meritocratic factors influence the hazard of becoming a full professor in sociology/demography in France. We use event history modeling on a longitudinal career dataset. This dataset is unique, as it combines non-anonymous statutory information for the complete population of sociologists and demographers recruited as assistant professors (in French, “*maîtres de conférences*”) between 2000 and 2020 at French sociology departments, allowing us to observe their career trajectories until 2021. The data come from the administrative records of the Human Resources Directorate (DGRH) of the French Ministry of Higher Education and Research (MESRI). We supplement this data with yearly information on publications, administrative tasks, awards, and institutional location, which we manually coded for each of the 658 individuals in our database. Moreover, MESRI data allow us to use individual-level information on applications for qualification (for which a habilitation thesis is a prerequisite), on qualifications, and on applications for full professorship positions. This enables us to distinguish between unconditional and conditional hazards of becoming a full professor and to identify the contribution of each stage of promotion to the overall gender gap. We also complement our longitudinal analysis with cross-sectional insights on recent recruitments (2009 to 2023).

With this analytical setup, we are able to test different meritocratic and non-meritocratic theories, while focusing on the extent to which the factors leading to a full professorship differ between women and men. We cover human capital by accounting for both quantitative and qualitative aspects of academic publishing, as well as significant administrative responsibilities. Symbolic capital is addressed by considering academic awards. We also consider the geographical location of the institution at first recruitment as an assistant professor, thereby capturing institutional prestige, network effects, and mobility aspects.

Our study contributes to prior research in several ways. The first contribution is technical: our study uses an original set of nonresponsive longitudinal data, whereas existing studies on academic careers often rely on either cross-sectional data or retrospective survey data. Cross-sectional data involve the risk of estimation bias due to endogeneity, and survey data may suffer from response bias caused by self-selection and self-reporting (Lutter & Schröder, 2016). Our longitudinal data, based on complete cohorts of assistant professors and combined with specifically coded bibliographic information, allow us to go beyond merely describing who becomes a full professor of sociology/demography in France. Using statistical models of duration, we identify the factors that promote, as well as those that impede, a successful academic career, distinguishing between demographic, geographic, and meritocratic aspects, as well as their interactions.

This rich empirical setup enables us to deliver substantive contributions. Our second contribution is thus to show the extent to which publication output is essential in becoming a full professor compared to other factors, and how the importance of academic publications depends on demographic and geographic aspects. Most importantly, we quantify the gender difference in the hazard of becoming a full professor in sociology/demography in France that remains after controlling for different aspects of human and symbolic capital. Third, we investigate explanatory patterns for the persisting gender gap among full professors in sociology/demography in France, beyond academic performance alone. We address not only the selection mechanisms in recruitment but also the selection and self-selection mechanisms of candidates.

Together, these three contributions provide a unique opportunity to investigate the gender gap in academic careers in France. Sociology/demography is an interesting field to study because it combines methodological tools from both the natural sciences and the humanities. As illustrated by a recent descriptive study [*self-identifying reference*], the percentage of women among assistant professors was around 56% in 2020, higher than in the technical sciences (34% on average in 2020) but slightly lower than in the languages, literature, and humanities group (58% on average in 2020). However, to date, only just over a third of all full professors in sociology/demography in France are women, even though the percentage has increased considerably over the last decades (12% in 1985, 23% in 2000). In 2020, women accounted for 37% of full professors in sociology/demography, which remains lower than the average in languages, literature, and humanities (42%) but higher than in technical sciences (19%).

Sociology/demography thus represents an intermediary discipline, making it a useful field of study even in relation to more distant disciplines.

The French academic labor market is interesting to study because assistant professors are offered permanent civil servant positions upon first recruitment (i.e., there is no ‘tenure track’ at public universities). However, this does not necessarily lead to a smaller gender gap among full professors compared to other countries. Women represented 28% of full professors in France in 2020 across all disciplines [*self-identifying reference*]. More generally, women make up less than one-third of full professors in France, similar to the EU-27 average (European Commission, 2024), the UK (Ellis, 2024), and the United States (AAUP, 2020)¹.

This article is organized as follows: Section 2 provides an overview of theoretical and empirical insights. Section 3 describes the French system of academic careers in sociology/demography. Section 4 details our data and methods, and Section 5 provides descriptive statistics. Section 6 presents our estimation results, distinguishing between different hazards: the unconditional hazard of becoming a full professor, the hazard of applying for qualification (once a habilitation thesis is written and defended), the hazard of becoming qualified conditional on applying for qualification, the hazard of applying for full professorship conditional on being qualified, and the hazard of becoming a full professor conditional on applying for a full professorship. In Section 7, we identify the contribution of gender gaps at each stage of promotion to the overall promotion gap. Finally, Section 8 summarizes our findings and discusses potential policy implications and avenues for future research.

2. Theory and existing empirical insights

2.1. *The determinants of promotion in academia*

In academia, academic performance is considered to play a major role in the promotion of academic careers. This idea goes back to human capital theory that generally assumes that those with the highest merits and achievements are rewarded with the best most desirable positions in the labor market (Durkheim 1893, Becker 1960).

To measure merits in academia, it is relatively consensual to consider scientific output, notably publications in academic journals and books, as these are known to play an important role in the promotion of academic careers and hence in becoming a professor across disciplines (Fox 1983, Long et al. 1993). Administrative responsibilities and teaching experience are two additional dimensions that are generally considered as important for becoming a full professor.

The definition of scientific productivity as well as the weighting between publications, administrative responsibilities and teaching, differs between, and sometimes also within disciplines. There exist, for example, different assessments about the ranking of published articles, books, textbooks, edited volumes, and book chapters. Whilst in natural sciences, such as physics, articles published in peer-reviewed journals are valued the most, Clemens et al. (1995) point out that among historians, articles are considered only as complementary to book that might better serve to expose thought-through arguments. Social sciences are situated between natural sciences and humanities, which may explain the existence of a multifaceted valuing of scholarly output (Clemens et al. 1995, Weisshaar 2017).

This is particularly the case for sociology in France, a discipline which has been constantly challenged and enriched over the last decades by the coexistence not only of different methodological approaches (for example quantitative vs. qualitative, inductive vs. deductive), but also of linguistic requirements (publications in French or English, in international or national outputs), of analytical procedures (descriptive vs. problematizing) and of ideas about co-authorship. The fact that in France, demography is part of sociology in the academic organization of disciplines, further contributes to the variability in

¹ EU-27: 27,3% on average in 2019, with lower figures for example in Germany (21%) and Italy (23%); USA: 33% in 2020, UK: 31% in 2022.

valuing different types of scientific output in this discipline. This underscores the importance of considering multiple publications outputs in sociology/demography in France.

In general, research output is considered to be a key determinant across disciplines for academic promotion (see Bosquet et al. 2019 for France). That this is valid for sociology has been shown for example for Germany (Jungbauer-Gans and Gross, 2013; Lutter and Schröder, 2013) or for Japan (Fujiwara, 2018). At the same time, there is consensus that besides the absolute number of publications, qualitative aspects of the scientific output should also be considered. However, while in France in neighboring disciplines such as economics/business, there is a broad agreement about the ranking of scientific journals in the field (see for example HCERES, 2021), there exist no such consensus in sociology. The last list of classified (albeit not ranked) journals in sociology/demography has been published in 2013 (AERES, 2013) in France, and since then there has been no longer a consensus list. Similar to balancing between articles and books, different ideas exist about coauthorship. While some jury members might appreciate a demonstrated ability to work in groups, others might value it more when scientists show their independence. This also applies to the choice of language of the publication. However, also in sociology in France, there is an increasing expectation to work according to international standards in order to become competitive not only for international, but also for national funding (see for example ANR, 2024). This implies a higher focus on (often multiple-authored and English) publications in double-blind peer-reviewed international review, at the expense of (often single-authored and French) books, book chapters and manuals.

Teaching and administrative tasks may also be considered as merit-based criteria enhancing the academic career, as pointed out by Sabatier et al. (2006) for sociology in France. The literature points, however, to a heterogeneous effect of teaching and administrative tasks. On the one hand, engagement in an institution such as being head of a research unit or being responsible for the organization of teaching can have a signaling effect, showing devotion, capacity for organization and leadership (Chenu and Martin, 2016). On the other hand, taking up administrative tasks also comes with the risk of having to reduce time spent on research and therefore of having a lower research output (Sabatier et al., 2006). The same time mechanism seems to be at hand regarding the impact of teaching activities. Chenu & Martin (2016) point out that investing time into teaching could be detrimental in an area where career advancements are primarily driven by individual productivity. Furthermore, Parker (2008) points out for the UK that considering the quantity and quality of teaching is often limited to junior professor positions, while the focus is often solely set on research excellence for promotions to full professors. Differences might exist between countries and disciplines concerning the weighting of teaching and administrative tasks. Subbaye and Vithal (2017), for example, have shown that in Australia and South Africa, teaching is explicitly mentioned as a promotion criterion. Wald and Goding (2020) suggest that outstanding administrative tasks like being head of a department can have positive effects on career progression towards full professorship. However, the increasing internationalization of the academic market makes it likely that across disciplines and countries, recruitment committees increasingly place emphasis on academic production and that special achievements in teaching and administration are only recognized as supplementary aspects.

Another signal of academic productivity beyond scholarly publications, teaching and administrative tasks is academic awards. Having received awards can act as a supplementary signaling device positively impacting promotion in academia (Fujiwara, 2018). More specifically, awards can imply high academic potential, capacity for innovation and even “conformity to established academic norms” all of which are criteria for high academic performance (Lutter & Schröder). Awards also call attention to the awarded scientists by peers, media, funding agencies and tenure committees (Meho, 2021). In this respect, awards may have a direct positive effect on promotion to a full professor, but also an indirect effect by increasing the probability of producing pioneering and innovative work from increased access to funding opportunities, which in turn further improves the chances of becoming a professor. Competitive grants and funding sources can thus also be considered as ‘academic awards’. In principle, grant funding should not increase the chances of becoming a full professor once scientific production is controlled for, as it provides an input into -rather than an output of- the research process (Plümper and Schimmelfennig, 2007).

However, grants and awards are mostly peer-reviewed and therefore ‘signal’ academic merit (Fujiwara, 2018). They may thus come with additional chances for a professorship specifically in disciplines where there is no consensus about the quality criteria of academic publications. After publications in SSCI-ranked journals, Lutter and Schröder (2016) for instance find that winning awards is the second strongest predictor for receiving tenure in sociology in Germany. Fujiwara (2018) even finds that acquiring competitive grants and funding sources is the strongest predictor of the chances of becoming a professor in Japan. These findings emphasize that awards and grants represent symbolic capital.

Further symbolic capital may consist in the signal that the institution at which a scientist spent his years (as PhD student, as post-doc or as assistant professor) sends about the individual’s academic capabilities. This “spillover effect” (Allison et al. 1982) exists in particular for countries with a clear hierarchy in academic institutions, such as in the United States or the UK (Lutter and Schröder, 2016). Pioneering studies of the role of symbolic capital in the US academic job market are those of Crane (1965) and Allison and Long (1987) who found that the best research departments in the US only hire students originating from the best departments, while those who come from universities with a comparably lower reputation are hired in less prestigious institutions after their PhD and are unlikely to close the gap in academic productivity and in chances of becoming a full professor that exists between them their competitors from more prestigious institutions. For France, however, Sabatier et al. (2015) find a limited effect of institutional prestige on the probability of receiving tenure and explain this with the lower stratification of the university system in France. Similarly, for sociology in Germany, Jungbauer-Gans and Gross (2013) and Lutter and Schröder (2016) find that the effect of the institution (PhD, assistant professorship) on becoming a full professor vanishes once scientific productivity is controlled for, suggesting a selection effect (the more productive scholars select into the more prestigious PhD programs and the more prestigious universities at recruitment as assistant professor).

Besides human and symbolic capital, the scholar’s scope of social capital or “academic inbreeding”, as termed by Godechot (2014), can also be crucial for promotion to a full professor. Social capital can be personal networks that are conducive to becoming a full professor, besides academic production (Zinovyeva and Bagues 2015; Lutter and Schröder 2016). These networks can imply greater access to non-public information or tacit knowledge about the hiring process, or the positive effect of knowing someone in the hiring committee. Individual social networks may notably be enlarged through membership in a research group and co-authorship, but also through participation in conferences and invitations as guest-speaker (Uhly et al., 2017).

In France, Godechot (2016) analyzed the effect of social capital on recruitment at the *École des Hautes Études en Sciences Sociales* (EHESS), a renowned French graduate research school training students up to PhD level in all social and human sciences among sociology and economics, between 1960 and 2005. He found that having a contact (PhD advisor, coauthor, colleague) in the hiring committee of the institution increases the chance of being put forward for recruitment by the electoral commission and increases the share of votes for a candidate (even if the jury member is not supposed to abstain from the vote).

In addition, Sabatier et al. (2006) mention mentoring as a powerful tool to enhance career prospects. Mentoring during the early career may build confidence and aspirations through the exchange of experiences and opportunities (as found by Van der Weijden, 2015 for the Netherlands). In addition, by proposing a candidate for promotion, a mentor may add leverage to the candidate’s profile during the evaluation processes (Bosquest, 2019). Finally, the propensity to collaborate may have an indirect as well as a direct positive impact on being promoted to a full professor. Directly, collaborative activity increases the scope of a researcher’s network. Indirectly, collaboration may also enhance scientific productivity through knowledge and skill exchange between researchers (Mairesse and Pezzoni, 2015).

Finally, mobility emerges as an increasingly important factor for career progression in academia across countries and disciplines. While most university value international mobility, the value is also determined by the destination, with US and English-speaking countries ranking the highest (Bauder et al. 2017; Seeber et al. 2023). Evidence from other countries and Europe suggests a limited effect of mobility on promotion, and international research visits are found to having to be rather short-term to not undermine local network effects (see for example Lawson and Shibayama, 2015 for Japan). A

negative light on mobility as a determinant for promotion is shed by Cruz-Castro & Sanz-Menéndez (2010) for the Spanish academic system. They find that tenure is awarded earlier to those who are not mobile. In line with this, Musselin (2004) points out that whilst French academics consider mobility as a crucial factor for career progression, loyalty to the domestic institution in which one pursued the first career steps seems to be valued in academic promotion in France. Similarly, Godechot and Louvet (2008) analyze the level of localism of professors who defended their PhD thesis between 1972 and 1996 in France and find that local candidates have been preferred to be hired in the French academic world as compared to foreign candidates. They also point towards the positive effects of academic inbreeding on efficiency in terms of avoiding the phenomenon of “turbo-teachers”, which are teachers who commute between their city of origin and that of assignment and who are said to invest considerably less into educational and administrative activities. Their findings are confirmed by a more recent analysis by Bojica et al. (2022), who state that the impact of mobility is country dependent: for France and Europe, as opposed to the US, empirical evidence suggests that loyalty weights more than mobility in the promotion to a professor. In France, however, important differences exist between disciplines. Some disciplines such as economics require a change of institute when applying for full professorship to undermine network effects, while others such as sociology do not. In any way, on an individual basis, being able to move -as well as not having to move- might both emerge as important factors when it comes to evaluate a scholar’s likelihood of becoming a full professor.

2.2. The gender gap in academic promotion

The above-mentioned theories bring forward three main arguments to explain why women are often underrepresented in academic careers. First, human capital theory emphasizes that men and women may differ in their levels of scientific productivity (difference model; Sonnert and Holton, 1995). Second, women may apply less for promotion in academia, even if equally ‘qualified’, i.e. equally productive than men. This mechanism of ‘self-selection’ of women into lower status positions in academia (Filandri and Pasqua, 2021) can be linked for example to different mobility, different preferences, different self-perception and/or different perception of the workplace climate in comparison to men (Spoon et al., 2023). Third, discrimination against women might be at play during the qualification and selection process of full professors (deficit model, Sonnert and Holton, 1995).

Lower productivity of women during their years as assistant professors may stem from the impact of motherhood. This impact can occur in the short run due to pregnancy and time spent with the child after birth, but can also occur in the middle and long run due to family obligations that may be higher for women in comparison to their male colleagues. In addition, due to their shorter reproductive time window, women are more prone than their male colleagues to start a family during their early career years (González Ramos et al., 2015). The higher caregiver responsibilities result thus in less time resources for women, which may affect not only their academic publishing record, but also their implications in collaborations and networks (Abramo, 2013) - therewith deteriorating women’s human, social as well as symbolic capital. scientific productivity (Chenu and Martin, 2016). Empirical research for France (CNRS and university physicists) by Mairesse & Pezzoni (2015) shows indeed that one of the main reasons for the gender productivity gap is that women have more frequent longer time spells with no publications, which could be related to their stronger engagement in motherhood, childcare and household duties. Loison et al. (2017) find that having a child reduces the probability of receiving tenure for women more than for men in France and Norway.

Mobility may also be affected for women as prime caregivers. This can not only reduce women’s participation in conferences and other academic events, as shown by Mairesse and Pezzoni (2015) for France, but also their propensity to accept a position that requires a relocation of the family or higher commuting time. Grant (2000) resumes that the tenure clock in academia assumes a researcher’s freedom from competing responsibilities such as family and benchmarks for when certain career points have to be attained to continue in the cycle of promotion, both of which are not in favor of women. Independent of the family status, however, women’s scientific productivity might also be reduced relative to men’s if women engage more than men during their early career years in teaching and other pedagogical and administrative responsibilities that are not visible and rewarded on the highest level

(Zuckerman and Cole, 1975). Whilst administrative responsibilities could signal leadership capacity and hence contribute to promotion to professor positions, they reduce time-resources spent for research and thus may yield the opposite result in an area where career advancements are dominantly driven by academic publishing. Sabatier et al. (2006) show indeed that in France (biology), women's involvement in administrative tasks reduces their odds of being promoted more than for men. At the same time, Chenu and Martin (2016) show for sociology and demography in France, that while women are generally more involved in administrative and teaching responsibilities than men, women are underrepresented in the most rewarding, top-level administrative tasks (such as heads of research units in CNRS and universities).

Self-selection of women comes at play if women avoid more than men the competitive process of promotion. In France, empirical evidence in economics suggests that the fact that women do not apply for the hiring process of full professors despite equal qualification contributes importantly to the gender gap in professor positions (Bosquet et al. 2019). Similar evidence is found for mathematics in the US (Ceci, 2018).

Lower applications for women may appear because women tend to be less confident than men about their abilities. In that case, women might either shy away from the competition or feel uncomfortable in taking part in it, which in turn can negatively impact their performance in the process (Niederle and Vesterlund, 2011). This, in turn, would reduce their probability of being promoted in comparison to men. However, rather than being less confident, it may also be that women are less willing to enter competition as they anticipate being discriminated against (Bosquet et al., 2019). Women may also apply less than men to full professorship positions because of higher constraints in terms of time and mobility. For example, by analyzing the decision-making procedure of junior faculty members in the US, Rivera (2017) finds that women consider their relationship and family status more than their male colleagues.

Another form of self-selection may be that women self-select towards specific subjects and tasks where they expect to be less discriminated against, and where they believe to be given greater opportunities for career development due to the greater presence of other women. Examples of such subjects are gender studies, sociology and social sciences, whilst natural sciences but also economics and finance seem to be more male-dominated. It could also be that women have a higher preference for humanities as well as for certain teaching and administrative services, maybe because they consider that they can make an important human contribution in this field (Park, 1996). However, career prospects for women are not necessarily higher in academic fields in which women are more represented, as it has been shown recently for France [*self-identifying reference*]. Chenu and Martin (2016) add that women may find themselves more than men in second-level administrative responsibilities (that are time-consuming but not necessarily career-enhancing), because in a world where women still retain the majority of childcare, they cannot engage in leadership positions in research (as research unit or department director) because meeting hours may not be compatible with parental obligations.

Discrimination might affect human, social and symbolic capital of women during their years as assistant professor, therewith lowering their chances to accumulate the capital that is necessary to apply for full professor positions (publication record, habilitation: authorization to conduct research). At the same time, gender discrimination can also take place in the committee hiring process of a full professor even if all candidates are similarly 'qualified'. Becker (1993, p.387) explains this form of pure discrimination with a dislike for an individual's characteristics in terms of gender, race or other. This is based on a psychological bias where decisions are also influenced by intuitions and feelings. In addition, statistical discrimination may come at play when individuals in the hiring committee make inferences about the applicant's productivity based on their group membership and not based on individual productivity (Phelps, 1972). Statistical discrimination is to be distinguished from taste discrimination because it focuses more specifically on productivity considerations.

Discrimination may occur if the work of female scientists is systematically undervalued and underrecognized in academia. This so called "Mathilda effect" has been put forward by Rossiter (1993) in honor of Matilda Joslyn Gage, a 19th-century thinker and feminist who highlighted the historical neglect of women's achievements, among them her own. The Mathilda effect postulates that the under recognition of women's contributions to academia results in systematic gender disparities across the

board in terms of publishing, co-authoring, citations, grants, as well as other social and symbolic capital (Dion et al., 2018). Empirical research by Sarsons (2017) considers the effect of co-authored papers on the probability of being tenured (in economics) and finds indeed that the impact of an additional co-authored paper on the probability of tenure differs by gender. An additional co-authored paper increases the probability of tenure by 8% for men whilst only by 2% for women. These findings point towards an implicit understanding that co-authoring women are likely to have contributed less or lower quality work than co-authoring men. The Mathilda effect is also empirically confirmed for citations (Dion et al., 2018) (as well as self-citations, i.e. women cite their own work less than their male counterparts; Lundberg and Stearns, 2019). Lundberg and Stearns (2019) suggest for economics in the US that women are held to higher standards and that they have to publish higher quality work to achieve the same as their male colleagues.

Abramo (2013) adds that the prevalence of masculine culture in academia may lead to the existence of a value system based on male characteristics reducing women's access to collaboration and research funds. Boschini and Sjogren (2007) suggest that in academia a mechanism of gender homophily is at play, by which collaborations primarily take place between colleagues of the same gender with whom one shares values as well as methodological approaches. As women remain a minority in academia particularly the more one advances to higher academic ranks (also recognized by the so-called glass-ceiling effect), the mechanism of gender homophily leads to the greater isolation of women and lower collaboration and social capital compared to men (Rivellini et al., 2006). The same mechanism may also be applied to mentoring. As aforementioned, mentoring can have a positive effect on academic promotion by building the confidence of young researchers and extending the social network. As fewer women progress towards senior positions in academia, there are fewer mentors for young women mentees who prefer to be mentored by women to exchange and build confidence regarding gender-specific obstacles to career advancement. This mechanism of gender homophily in a male-dominated arena may exacerbate gender inequalities across generations of researchers.

Besides undermining women's scientific production and visibility, gender discrimination may also be at play when it comes to the distribution of administrative and pedagogical responsibilities. In male-dominated arenas, stereotypes about women's authoritative capacity may reduce their prevalence in research leadership positions and limit women to lower-level administrative tasks that may not necessarily be less time consuming but less rewarding.

Empirical evidence on discrimination is, however, ambiguous. Weisshaar (2017) analyses the gender gap in tenure receipt in sociology, English literature and computer sciences in the US and finds that in all three disciplines, a significant gender gap in favor of men remains even after controlling for productivity and department characteristics.

For France, recent empirical studies suggest that overall, direct discrimination in academic recruitment cannot be excluded from the important factors explaining the underrepresentation of women among full professors (Devineau et al., 2018), and women continue to be relatively less favored than men both when they are local candidates and when they are external candidates (Godechot et al., 2025).

More specifically for certain disciplines in France, Sabatier and al. (2006) find for biology no evidence for lower odds of promotion to full professor for women once controlled for scientific productivity. This does, however, not exclude that scientific productivity itself is reduced for women due to discrimination. For economics in France, Bosquet et al. (2019) also find that women do not have significantly different returns to publications when 'equally productive'. For other countries, some empirical studies find even that women have an advantage of being promoted in comparison to men once scientific productivity is held 'constant' such as Williams and Ceci (2015) for biology, engineering and psychology in the US, Carlsson et al. (2021) for economics, law, physics, political science, psychology, and sociology in Iceland, Norway and Sweden, and Jungbauer-Gans and Gross (2013) as well as Lutter and Schröder (2016) for sociology in Germany. The finding that committee members have slightly advantaged women over men in some countries and disciplines over the most recent years might be due to gender-mainstreaming guidelines, gender-sensitive appointment protocols and/or professionally trained equal opportunity officers (Solga et al. 2023). At the same time, a greater presence of women in hiring

committees does not emerge as favoring women in several empirical studies, such as for example by Bagues et al. (2017) or by Bol et al. (2022).

For sociology in France, to our knowledge to date there exists no empirical study of the odds of becoming a full professor that attempts to quantify and explain an eventually remaining gender bias once scholarly publications and other factors are controlled for. There is, however, some descriptive evidence for promotions in sociology and demography in France by Chenu and Martin (2016), suggesting that a glass ceiling exists for women for becoming a full professor, typically around the age of 50, which is considerably stronger than that of becoming an associate professor around the age of 40. In a similar vein, Boudesseul (2023) looks at the participation of sociologists at congresses of the French Association for Sociology between 2004 and 2021 and finds that whilst the ratio of women to men in sociology professor positions has increased, men are still twice as likely to hold these positions in 2021, compared to three times as likely in 2004.

Overall, hitherto empirical research on the gender gap in academia suggests that in comparison to other disciplines, sociology is affected by a larger variety of ambiguous effects, which may explain the inconsistent results in different countries. For example, in sociology, criteria for publications and career assessment are less strict in comparison to natural sciences and more math-based social sciences like economics. This larger range may, on the one hand, promote scientific production particularly for women (Auriol et al., 2022). In the other hand, the lack of clear criteria may leave more space for bias and discrimination against women (Ginther and Kahn, 2021).

Further empirical evidence is thus needed to identify the different mechanisms that are at play for academic promotions in sociology. The fact that sociology is on the intersection between hard and soft disciplines makes sociology an interesting field, but also represents an important methodological challenge when it comes to measure scientific productivity.

Another major methodological challenge stems from the fact that an important set of information is often unavailable in studies that empirically assess academic promotion. In many studies, data on the career path of researchers is obtained by using state or ministry data sources (Mairesse and Pezzoni, 2016, Sabatier et al. 2006), in which other relevant information such as marital status, number of children, previous institutions of the researcher or publication records are missing. Additional information is gathered with different methods, such as sending questionnaires to researchers (Plümper and Schimmelfennig 2007, Jungbauer-Gans and Gross 2013, Loison et al. 2017) and/or scanning the internet for information on publications and other CV information (Lutter and Schröder, 2016, Auriol et al. 2022). Potential biases may hereby arise due to self-reporting in survey data as well as due to presence and survivorship in the internet. To obtain coherent time-series on publications, individual information on CVs and publications has been manually coded from personal or departmental web pages in several recent studies (Lutter and Schröder 2016, Weishaar 2017). However, when based solely on individuals having web pages, here again, survivor effects may be large, and gender-specific assessments may be importantly influenced by sample bias. A combination of ministry data, which provides time-series of the career status of complete cohorts of academics, and a manual web scanning of the publications of each individual emerges thus as a method that reduces measurement bias as much as possible. The therewith obtained time-series data allows a modelling of the odds of becoming a full professor by considering potential gender biases at different stages of the career, whilst holding unobservable characteristics of individuals constant. However, the manual web scanning is highly resource and time-intensive, and may not only be subject to potential coding errors (Lutter and Schröder, 2016) but also to selection bias (the information available online might differ highly among individuals depending on productivity, gender, institutional affiliation etc.).

3. Academic careers in sociology: the French case

Assistant professors (*“maître de conférences des universités”* in French) and full professors (*“professeurs des universités”* in French) are two types of French civil servants whose main characteristics have remained constant since their creation in 1984 (decree 84-431 of June 6). Both are part of the

permanent academic staff and as lecturer-researchers (labeled “*enseignants-chercheurs*” in French), they have both to combine teaching and research.

A distinctive feature of the French academic system is the absence of a tenure-track model. Academic staff are recruited directly into permanent civil-service positions, with tenure granted after a short probationary period. As a result, individuals appointed at a level roughly equivalent to *assistant professor* are effectively tenured from the outset. This is why the French rank *maître de conférences* is sometimes translated as *associate professor*, even though the individual may have joined the academic staff only recently. For the sake of simplicity, throughout this article we refer to *maître de conférences* as **AP** (for assistant/associate professor) and to *full professor* as **FP**.

Unlike other civil servants, French citizenship is not required, neither for AP nor for FP. And unlike other civil servants, they benefit from free speech rights, as teachers and as researchers. Also, unlike other civil servants, their career depends upon peer evaluation, at a national range by the National Council of Universities (“*Conseil national des universités*” in French -CNU-, responsible for academic qualifications and promotions) divided in disciplinary sections, and at a local range by disciplinary recruitment committees (in French “*commissions de spécialistes*” renamed “*comités de sélection*” in 2008) specially constituted for each position to be filled, and by the multidisciplinary scientific board of their university. A majority of the CNU members and of the local boards is elected by the corresponding faculty. Sociology and demography are both classified under Section 19 of the CNU in France, meaning that scholars in both fields are evaluated within the same national section. For the sake of simplicity, throughout this article we refer to “sociology” when analyzing transitions to full professorship of sociologists and demographers in France.

Becoming an AP or FP requires a “qualification” by the CNU and a selection at the local level. To apply for qualification to AP, candidates must have a doctoral thesis, and to apply for qualification to FP, candidates must have a Habilitation to Supervise Research (“habilitation à diriger des recherches” in French: HDR). The HDR is a postdoctoral qualification required in France to supervise PhD students and to apply for full professorships. Lighter and more flexible than the huge “thèse d’Etat” (required to access professorship from 1962 to 1984, while a far shorter “thèse de troisième cycle” was needed to become “maître de conférences”), the HDR implies the defense of a set of books, articles, manuscripts, and, necessarily, a synthesis of past activities attesting the ability to lead research projects². Since 2020, the “qualification” by the central CNU is no more required among AP who apply to a full professor position, having a HDR is enough. Recruitment of full professors takes place on a local level in sociology in France. The qualified candidates must apply for each open position and are auditioned and ranked by a local jury that consists of internal and external members. AP in sociology in France can apply for external as well as for internal FP positions, i.e. they are not required to change the university to become FP.

Inside each of the categories of AP and FP, the basic wages increase along national scales made of two types of steps: “echelons” automatically passed according to the length of service, and “classes” accessed through choices made by peers, half at a national range, half at a local one. For AP, the scale included two classes (2nd class, 1st class), then three (since 1989, 2nd class, 1st class, “hors classe”) and two again (“classe normale”, “hors classe³”) after the suppression of the 2nd class. FP follow a three-class scale (2nd class, 1st class, “classe exceptionnelle”).

² The requested HDR content varies by discipline and over time. In sociology, an HDR dossier usually includes a synthesis (habilitation manuscript) of about 100 to 200 pages presenting the candidate’s research trajectory, major contributions, and future research agenda. This is not necessarily a single new thesis but can also be a reflective overview of the candidate’s published and ongoing work. The dossier also includes a collection of publications, sometimes an original research component, and often a supervision and teaching statement. The HDR is defended publicly before a jury of senior academics, typically including several external members. The HDR is usually obtained several years after the PhD (often 10 to 15 years in sociology).

³ Once reaching the “hors classe” grade, the incentives for AP to apply for FP positions become relatively weak, as the salary gap narrows and career stability is already secured. Indeed, the pay scale of AP “hors classe” corresponds roughly to that of the lowest grade of FP (2nd class). Nevertheless, the professional prestige associated with FP positions remains higher.

As illustrated by Figure A in the appendix, the proportion of women among academics since 1985 in sociology in France (section 19: sociology and demography combined) has increased considerably. Amongst AP, the proportion of women rose from 28.80% in 1985 to 56.25% in 2020. Amongst FP, the proportion of women rose from 12.39% in 1985 to 36.85%. However, the significant feminization of the academic staff does not necessarily imply a substantial convergence between men and women in the academic career track. This is suggested by the observation that the proportion of FP amongst female academics rose from 13.33% in 1985 to only 20.22% in 2020 in sociology in France, while the proportion of FP amongst male academics was, with 35.83% in 2020, much higher (and already as high as 30.56% in 1985).

In 2020, the professor-to-assistant professor ratio is still much more favorable for men in sociology in France. When computing a single composite index comparing the professor-to-assistant professor ratio amongst women to the professor-to-assistant professor ratio amongst men (descriptive equivalent of an odds ratio), we obtain 0.35 for the year 1985 and 0.45 for the year 2020. This implies that in the year 2020, there were still roughly only half as many FP per AP among women as among men. If the rate of change observed between 1985 and 2020 continues at the same pace, gender parity in the FP-AP ratio could be reached only after several decades.

With 0.45, the CNU-section 19 (Sociology & Demography) had the second lowest odds ratio amongst the nine human science disciplines in France⁴. However, the average odds ratio in this group⁵ was, with 0.48 in 2020 not much higher and the odds ratio was similarly low in all disciplines in France in 2020. It scored on average 0.48 in 2020 (52 CNU sections combined), with 0.51 on average in Literary & Human Sciences, 0.48 in Law, Economics & Business and 0.45 in Sciences. Thus, within each major disciplinary group, the number of FP per AP was still about twice as low for women as for men on average and no discipline has approached gender parity at the most recent date observed. For more detailed cross-sectional annual information by section and disciplinary groups as well as information on the underlying database, see [*self-identifying reference*].

4. Data and methods

4.1. The database

To empirically investigate the determinants of the transition to full professor in Sociology in France, we now switch from a cross-sectional to a longitudinal approach. We hereby use event-history models on a unique panel dataset that covers full career profiles of all sociologists who were recruited as AP (*maître de conférences*: MCF) between the years 2000 and 2020 at French universities⁶. Statistical data on tenured academics come from the administrative records of the Human Resources Directorate (DGRH) of the French Ministry of Higher Education and Research (MESRI)⁷. These records provide annual information on the stock and flows of academic staff, including variables such as corps, grade, gender, age, CNU section, institution, and seniority within the corps. We dispose thus of a non-anonymous

⁴ Only the CNU-section 20 (Ethnology, Prehistory & Biological anthropology) scored lower, with an odds ratio of 0.35 in 2020.

⁵ Psychology, Philosophy, Architecture (theory and practice) & Arts, Sociology & Demography, Ethnology & Prehistory & Biological Anthropology, History (Ancient and Medieval Worlds), History (Modern/Contemporary Worlds), Physical & Human & Economic & Regional Geography, Spatial Planning & Urbanism.

⁶ Note that in our sample, we only consider transitions from “maître de conférences” (referred to as AP in this article) to full professors (referred to as FP in this article). Not considered here are “assistants”, “attachés temporaires d’enseignement et de recherche”, “chargés de cours”, “vacataires”, “chargés d’enseignement”, “moniteurs”, “PRAG” (“professeurs agrégés” of the high school level), or “personnels associés de statut temporaire” (PAST, associated “maîtres de conférences” or “professors”, supposed to hold a main occupation out of the university). Their common distinctive feature is that no doctoral thesis is required to fill these jobs. They belong to a changing tangle of statuses, but due to their few numbers they are statistically negligible at a national range.

⁷ The data analyzed in this article were made available to the authors by the Ministry of Higher Education, Research and Innovation (MESRI) under a data-sharing agreement dated March 31, 2022.

dataset that delivers basic demographic information (name, forename, date of birth) of all individuals assigned as AP and FP in a given year at a French university. In addition, the DGRH provided us with individual-level data on applications and recruitments for academic positions, available in digital form since 2009.

For tracing academic careers in sociology, we select individuals who enter the academic career track between the years 2000 and 2020 as AP in sociology (disciplinary CNU section 19) and follow them until the year 2021. Our database therewith covers 88 French university establishments which are under the supervision of the Ministry of higher education and research (MESRI). Not covered are certain specific bodies which are not supervised by the CNU, such as *Collège de France* or EHESS (*École des hautes études en sciences sociales*)⁸. However, associate professors who are assigned to academic institutions that correspond to the French concept of ‘*grande école*’ rather than to ‘university’ are included in our database, as long as they are employed by the Ministry of higher education and research (MESRI)⁹.

We therewith cover 658 individuals, who entered a French sociology department as AP between the years 2000 and 2020. We refer to them as AP of “cohorts” 2000 to 2020 in this manuscript. 307 of them are men, and 351 women. Among these AP, 110 have become full professors at a French university until the year 2021. 69 of them are men, and 41 women. This implies that, overall, in our sample of French sociologists who have been recruited as AP between years 2000 and 2020, women have had only half the chances of men to become full professors until 2021. More detailed descriptive statistics of our sample can be found in section 6.1.

When estimating the overall hazard ratio of becoming a full professor, we observe all transitions of AP in sociology to a full professorship at a French university, independent of the discipline of destiny. We restrict the analysis of transitions to full professorship in sociology/demography only (section 19) in robustness checks, however. In the later analysis, when estimating more specific hazard ratios (of becoming qualified by CNU, and of becoming full professor conditioned on applying) we restrain our sample to those who seek promotion in the field of sociology/demography (section 19) only.

Amongst the 110 individuals for whom we observe a transition to full professor, the large majority becomes full professor in sociology/demography (section 19), while 12 individuals become full professors in other disciplines (in human sciences and education sciences mostly¹⁰). Recruitments of full professors in sociology/demography (section 19) coming from other disciplines or from abroad are not included in our empirical analysis (5 individuals only over the observed period).

Note also that we focus on full academic profiles in our core analysis. We exclude thus individuals who exit our data base before becoming a full university professor at a French university. ‘Exits’ refer to individuals who definitely leave the status of permanent academic staff (“*enseignant-chercheur*”) at a French university under MESRI supervision. Individuals who change the academic ‘section’ of sociology/demography or the university establishment within MESRI (“mutation”) during their years as AP are kept in the data base. The selection criteria is to have entered as AP (*maître de conférences*) a sociology department (section 19) at a French university under MESRI supervision between 2000 and 2020. Several reasons can lead individuals to exit, such as a cessation of professional activity (due to sickness, retirement, or other reasons), alternative career options outside academia (Ministries, private sector), moving abroad (to follow a call as full professor, or for other reasons) or a new position at a French academic institution that is not under MESRI supervision. It cannot be excluded that these exits are correlated with academic productivity and with gender. Both the least and the most productive may be most attracted by outside options. However, in the French case, we observe only a small number of

⁸ The EHESS (School for Advanced Studies in the Social Sciences) is a selective public school in social sciences, under the supervision of the Ministry of Higher Education and Research (MESRI). Sociologists at Collège de France and EHESS represent only a very small fraction of university sociologists in France, while their scientific publishing records are likely to be above average.

⁹ Assistant or associate professors employed on private contracts (tenure tracks) are thus not included in our analysis, such as at FNPS (Fondation Nationale de Sciences Politique – Sciences Po Paris) for example.

¹⁰ Political science (2), EHESS (1), education science (4), human sciences (5).

exits of AP without re-entries over the observed time period in sociology (45 individuals out of a total of 703 individuals in our database: 6%). We keep individuals who exit our database after having become full professors, as we are able to observe their transition to full professor (6 individuals).

The low number of exits may be due to the French specificity that AP are directly tenured at their first recruitment and therefore do not have to leave academia unless “on their own will”. As we dispose only of 45 exits of AP in our database, we drop AP who exited the database for our core analysis, to focus on full career profiles only¹¹. We run, however, an alternative empirical analysis allowing us to treat exits of AP as a distinct event besides the transition from AP to FP.

There are also a few cases of AP who temporarily leave their function at a French university under MESRI supervision (31 individuals) in our data base. Amongst those 31 individuals, 20 left the academic sector because they were temporarily detached from their function. This leave-of-absence-status, known as ‘*détachement*’ in the French system (secondment), allows civil servants to leave and re-enter their public-sector job for other missions in the public sector (such as for example work in ministries, municipalities etc.). The remaining 11 individuals were temporarily ‘inactive’ due to sick leave. We keep these individuals in our sample of potential candidates for full professorship, and control for secondment and inactivity statuses explicitly in our regression analysis.

AP who benefit from a teaching reduction or from a teaching cessation, during a certain time period due to the French system of ‘*délégation*’ (similar to a sabbatical accorded on request, due to maternity, a thematic change in the research topic, a research affiliation at IUF, CNRS, or any other academic partner institutions), are also kept in the data base, as they continue being employed by the Ministry of higher education and research (MESRI) during this time. We control for research delegations in our regression analysis.

4.2. The empirical setup

In our empirical analysis of the gender gap in academic promotion in sociology in France, we mobilize information about several stages of promotion. We do not dispose of information on candidates and outcomes of the habilitation (HDR) procedure, but we dispose of information about candidates and outcomes of the qualification process that follows the habilitation process and that has been mandatory to become eligible for full professorship until the year 2020 (as described in section 3). We also possess information on candidacies for full professorships in sociology.

This enables us to consider five possible outcomes:

- 1) The unconditional hazard of becoming full professor.
- 2) The hazard of applying for qualification (once a HDR is written and defended).
- 3) The hazard of becoming qualified conditioned on applying for qualification.
- 4) The hazard of applying for full professorship conditioned on being qualified.
- 5) The hazard of becoming full professor conditioned on applying for full professorship.

For each outcome, we first estimate the hazard ratio while controlling for gender, with and without further control variables. The additional control variables (scientific productivity amongst others) enable us to identify factors that are significantly correlated with career progression, independent of gender. We then estimate the full specifications with all controls separately for men and women, enabling us to identify factors that have a differential impact on career progression between men and

¹¹ Profiles of 45 exits: 30 retirements, 3 professors abroad, 5 professors at private academic institutions, 1 resignation, 4 career changes, 2 deaths.

women. A decomposition analysis finally reveals the contribution of each stage of promotion to the overall gender gap in promotion.

As our data set covers full career profiles of all AP in sociology in France employed since 2000, we are able to apply event-history models to estimate the different hazards of promotion. In these ‘survival’ models, in general, the main variable of interest is the time from the event of recruitment as AP to recruitment as FP. The main response variable is thus the duration spent in origin state (assistant professorship) until transition to the destination state (full professorship), while time-constant as well as time-varying covariates can be included (which are of our main interest). A special estimation method is needed because of right-censoring: For some observed individuals, the time of the event is not known because the event has not happened yet, by the end of the observed period. In addition, left-truncation implies that individuals for which the event happened before the beginning of the observation period are excluded.

As our main interest lies in the time-constant and time-varying covariates rather than in time, we use a series of nested Cox-regressions (Cox, 1972) to estimate the factors that increase or decrease the odds that our event of interest occurs, i.e. that an AP becomes FP. The non-parametric model performs coefficient estimations without assuming a baseline hazard function (i.e. without having to assume a fixed shape for the survival curve). This implies that it is not necessary to model time explicitly in a Cox-regression. Durations are, however, illustrated by survival curves in the descriptive results-section.

In the estimation results section, we display hazard ratios to facilitate the interpretation of estimation results, implying that an effect is positive if the hazard ratio above 1, and negative if below 1.

In our estimation models, we use robust, panel-corrected standard errors clustered by persons to adjust for non-independence of observation (Lin and Wei, 1989). The models rely on the Efron method for tied events (Cleves et al, 2004).

We observe individuals since their first year of recruitment as AP and until (including) the year the AP becomes FP or until the end of our study’s timeframe (2021). This yields an unbalanced panel data set, in which the number of entries per AP equals the number of years from recruitment as AP until the event occurs (becoming FP) or until the timeframe ends (year 2021). Table A in the appendix displays and comments on a simplified example of our data structure. Independent variables are coded cumulative over time when time-variant (publications, administrative responsibilities, delegations, grants). All other independent variables (age at recruitment as AP, gender, Paris-location at first recruitment as AP) are time-constant. The productivity indexes are thus incremented on a yearly basis and do not include events occurring after the promotion from AP to FP for those who have been promoted.

We use absolute values for the independent variables, assuming linear relation, which is the most restrictive model. However, results also hold when using logged values, which allows for possible nonlinear effects and non-linear marginal returns. It is possible, for example, that publications have decreasing marginal returns, as an additional publication may have a higher effect at a lower number of publications. Results based on logged values for publications confirm the robustness of our findings and are available on request.

4.3. Measures of scientific production

For the 658 observed individuals recruited as AP in sociology between years 2000 and 2020, we coded CV information and publications from personal and professional web pages (google scholar, HAL, research gate, CVs online, department/research center website, google books etc.). We hereby identified individuals by using the family name (and the maiden name if applicable), the forename as well as the university and department (section) affiliation of individuals provided by the non-anonymous dataset coming from the French Ministry of higher education and research (MESRI). To attribute information about scientific production that is available online to the individuals in our database, we matched manually the 658 individuals in our database with publication information available online, one-by-one. The authors and two research assistants coded the data during the years 2022 and 2023. Codings were

double-checked by a second coder. Validity checks were performed on the data to correct coding errors (various observed individuals checked and confirmed their coded data, as well as intercoder reliability tests).

We did not use automated processes (web scraping of google scholar, for example), as they did not deliver sufficient data quality¹². We also decided against creating a list of relevant journals and book editors and then seeing who amongst the individuals in our data base has published in them (backwards method), as establishing such a list is very controversial among French sociologists (AERES, 2013) and French sociologists do not tend to limit their publications to a manageable number of journals¹³.

We collected scientific production (articles and books), administrative responsibilities, as well as awards and grants on a yearly basis. We measure scientific production by the accumulated number of publications at time t . To not only take into account quantitative but also qualitative aspects, we distinguish between several types of publication. We first run a general specification based on the overall accumulated number of articles as well as overall accumulated number of books, and then distinguish between: top articles, classified articles, non-classified articles, articles as sole author, articles in English, books as sole author, books in English, edited volumes and textbooks.

As mentioned before, classifying journals in which French sociologists publish is a difficult undertaking and represents a subject of research on its own. We nevertheless propose two attempts in order to capture at least some qualitative aspects of academic publishing: We identify articles in 16 double-blind peer-reviewed journals that are generally considered as high-level 'flagship'-journals in the international as well as French community of sociologists and demographers, due to their high impact-factor and strong selectivity (time-constant category of 'top'-articles)¹⁴. The composition of this list, as well as its assumed temporal stability, is open to debate and constitutes a subject in its own right, one that extends beyond the scope of the present study. However, the list allows us a broad distinction between different ways of academic publishing by highlighting publications in journals that are doubtlessly of continuous high quality and competitiveness¹⁵.

We also identify articles published in journals that were classified by AERES (French agency for the evaluation of academic research and teaching) between the years 2008 and 2013 (time-varying category of 'classified articles' between years 2008 and 2013, time-constant for years 2000-2008 and 2014-2020). We do not classify book editors due to too high dispersion in the field. We used the AERES- rather than the SSCI-classification (Social Sciences Citation Index) to suit the specific French context. In its latest classification, AERES listed 238 journals for the field of sociology and demography, without further discrimination¹⁶. The committee verified for each journal that it had the formal attributes identified by

¹² We compared our manually coded information about scientific productivity of individuals with the one obtained with several web scraping methods and found that the automated processes yield much less reliable results, mainly caused by error in the identification of individuals (same name and forename, but different fields, for example) as well as by error in the correct quantification of relevant publications (count of working papers, conference proceedings etc.). Results available on request.

¹³ We tried, however, to establish a list of academic journals and book editors based on the publication record of French sociologists who have been granted with a frog reward (PEDR, REPEC 3) over the last 5 years, in the hope of identifying a decent number (20 to 50) of relevant publication formats for French sociologists, but we yielded similar coverage for several hundred journals, including journals of other disciplines and various other languages besides French and English.

¹⁴ In alphabetical order: American Journal of Sociology, American Sociological Review, Annual Review of Sociology, Demography, Economie et Statistique, Espace Population et Société, European Sociological Review, Journal of Marriage and the Family, Population, Population and Development Review, Revue Française de Sociologie, Sociological Review, Sociologie du Travail, Sociologies, Sociology, Travail, Genre et Société.

¹⁵ Note that more recent interdisciplinary publication formats pointing to very high quality and impact (open access, low number of pages) such as Nature, Sciences, PNAS etc. have not been listed by AERES between 2008 and 2013. We yielded inconsistent regression results when including them as a separate category, because the number of publications in these formats by French assistant professors in sociology/demography was quite low until the year 2020.

¹⁶ https://3sif.fr/IMG/pdf/aeres_socio_demo.pdf

the AERES Reference Framework (AERES 2013, p. 26), as to its identification, its dissemination, its selection methods, its scientific quality, its editorial policy and its radiation. Note that several journals from related disciplines can also be found on this list (for example political sciences, economics or psychology).

9 out of the 15 journals we listed as ‘flagship’ journals and 117 out of the 238 journals listed by AERES publish in English. We further identify articles and books published in English language to broaden our attention to authors who reach out to an international audience by publishing beyond the listed journals.

Books cover monographs as well as dissertation and habilitation theses published by publishing houses. In addition, we account for edited volumes and textbooks in separate categories, but not for book chapters, reports, working papers and book reviews.

Co-authorship is taken into account by allowing a special focus on articles and books published as a sole author. We do not adjust each publication by the number and order of authors. Academic rules and customs concerning the order of authors vary broadly between disciplines/fields and over time, and therefore do not allow us to clearly identify lead-authorship. The same is true for number of authors, which tends to be increasing over time in particular in those fields that are closer to natural sciences (quantitative sociology and demography, for example, especially when related to health). This would necessitate a field- and time-varying adjustment, which certainly is worth exploring, but which is beyond scope of this article.

Note that impact factors of journals, articles and individuals are not considered, as this information is not available retrospectively (H-Index available on google scholar, for example).

4.4. Control variables

Our event-history models implicitly control for the duration until the event of transition to full professor occurs. It is likely that after a certain duration, AP are less likely to candidate for full professorship positions, due to the possibility in French academia of obtaining a special status as assistant professor (“*MCF hors classe*”) that comes with an increased wage (after five years of service at least; position created in 1989, as detailed in section 3). This means that the wage premium that comes with a full professorship decreases over time for assistant professors, which is captured by the control for duration.

The dataset provided by MESRI contains basic demographic information such as sex and date of birth, allowing us to observe the age at recruitment as AP, as well as -if applicable- at transition to FP. Unfortunately, we do not dispose of further demographic information, i.e. marital status, number of children, location of residence etc. Information about institutional affiliation allows us to distinguish between different types of establishments, observed at the first recruitment as AP. The MESRI database distinguishes between ‘*école d’ingénieurs*’ (engineering schools), ‘*établissements fusionnés*’, ‘*universités droit et économie*’, ‘*université lettres et sciences humaines*’, ‘*universités pluridisciplinaires et de santé*’ and ‘*universités pluridisciplinaires hors santé*’. The university landscape in France has been subject to important transformations over the last two decades, including recent efforts to group universities together. This makes it difficult to establish a clear and rather time-constant categorization as well as to properly identify universities or departments which are the most ‘prestigious’ (Cour des comptes, 2023). Therefore, rather than classifying establishments according to type or prestige, we contrast establishments which are located in and close to Paris to those outside Paris¹⁷.

This simple classification allows us capturing several spheres that might affect the transition to full professorship and its eventual gender gap, above and beyond the rather vague concept of prestige. Parisian establishments are not necessarily of higher academic prestige, but they might offer larger extra-

¹⁷ All universities having “Paris” in their name are coded as Parisian establishments, i.e. also those which are very close to Paris, such as for example Université Paris 10 (situated in Nanterre), Université Paris 8 (situated in Saint-Denis) or Université Paris Saclay.

institutional networks due to the geographical proximity of other institutions situated in and around Paris. This might be of particular benefit in times of an increasing demand for external recruitment to undermine internal network effects. An assistant professor starting the academic career in or close to Paris might also benefit from the fact that the Parisian region concentrates academic institutions that are among those in France offering the highest number of full professorships in sociology.

In addition, the geographical proximity of academic options might encourage potential candidates to consider full professorship because a successful application does not come with the cost of having to move. It might also be that settling in or close to Paris during the early stages of an academic career facilitates accepting full professorship in other parts of France, as Paris is situated in the heart of France and is well connected in terms of transport. The possibility of accepting a position in a different region because it is possible to commute and therefore does not necessitate to move the family might be particularly relevant for the decision to apply for full professorships. One could also think that working in Paris as an assistant professor allows the family to live elsewhere due to commuting possibilities, and this increased mobility broadens the application radius.

In any case, it is possible that assistant professors whose careers are already anchored in and around Paris benefit from higher network effects and face less mobility costs, and are therefore better situated to project themselves as full professors, which might encourage ex-ante productivity as well as starting the qualification/application process (i.e. writing a ‘habilitation’). It is also thinkable that there is a gendered impact of the Paris location. The literature suggests that career effects of both networks and mobility can be more beneficial for women (Nikunen and Lempiäinen, 2018; Lee et al. 2021).

We do not consider the localization and type of the academic institution which issued the Master and PhD degree, as this information is not available in the MESRI data base, and as we were not able to sufficiently cover this information based on our manual online search. Publications are usually listed online, but not all assistant professors post their entire CV online. For the same reason, we cannot control for post-doc studies, studies abroad, and awards and scholarships that were received before first recruitment as assistant professors.

Teaching is also not accounted for (neither in quantity nor quality), as information about past courses cannot be accessed for everyone. Besides, teach load reductions might be endogenous to our publication variables. Due to insufficient traceability, we can also not account for common administrative responsibilities such as directions of seminars, study courses or Master programs, for example, nor for participations in juries or boards, nor for conference organizations etc.

We do, however, take into account a series of extraordinary merits, for which information can usually be found online, even if not shared by the person concerned. This applies to certain high-level administrative responsibilities such as university president or vice-president, head of research center and head of department. We coded this information whenever available online, with possible lacunas. We also coded outstanding symbols of academic merit whenever available online, such as ERC and ANR grants, CNRS medals, as well as delegations labelled as ‘scientific excellence’ such as those granted by LABEX, IUF or CNRS. These signs of academic merit are likely to be endogenous to our publication variable and should normally turn out insignificant in a regression that includes publications. However, it is possible that these signs increase an individual’s academic reputation beyond the publication record (“signaling effect”), which is why we decided to include this control in our full specifications.

We also control for discontinuity in the career profiles due to secondment and inactivity. Finally, we include year-fixed effects to account for changes in the opportunity structure of the academic labor market over time. These might be caused by changes in the number of open professorship positions per year. While the number of full professorships in sociology in France opened to recruitment increased significantly in the 1990s due to the growth of the student population, it has declined since the 2000s¹⁸.

¹⁸ Number of open full professorship positions in sociology in France: 30 in 2010, 16 in 2015, 14 in 2020. Only since 2021, the number of available positions has risen slightly (18 in 2021, 24 in 2022, 23 in 2023), in response to the increase in retirements among university faculty. With the aim of improving the FP/AP ratio to 40/60 (i.e.

Opportunities might also change over time because of changes in the number and profile of competing candidates for full professorship positions in sociology/demography in France (including those from abroad and from other disciplines). Inter-disciplinary and international mobilities make it difficult to explicitly quantify these labor market aspects in our empirical regressions, but year-fixed effects help us capture these aspects. In addition, opportunities might change over time because of time-varying profiles of jury members who recruit full professors in sociology/demography at French universities (discipline/field, institutional affiliation, sex, international affiliation, explicit and implicit recruitment criteria etc.). Ultimately, opportunities might change over time because of time-varying thematic orientations within the field of sociology/demography of open positions and of candidates. We do not model these factors explicitly, as this is beyond the scope of our analysis. For the same reason, we ignore time-varying demographic aspects of the hiring departments in terms of size and sex composition. A series of qualitative and experimental studies suggest that these aspects are known to be associated with a gender bias in academic hiring (Pigeyre et Sabatier 2011, Régner et al. 2019). Our use of year-fixed effects allows, however, to reduce to some extent the estimation bias that is induced by unobserved time-variations in promotion opportunities.

5. Descriptive statistics

Table 1 describes the transitions to full professorship we observe for each cohort of assistant professors (AP), ranging from cohort 2000 to cohort 2020 (year of recruitment as assistant professor).

[Table 1 around here]

The first line corresponds to cohort 2000 and reads as follows:

Amongst the 33 AP in sociology that were recruited by French universities in year 2000, 23 were male and 10 were female. This corresponds to a proportion of women of 30% (column 11: %W). Amongst these 33 AP, 14 became university professors between years 2001 and 2021, which corresponds to 42% (column 8: %FP). 10 of those who became full professors were men, and 4 were women. This implies that amongst the men of cohort 2000, 43% became full professors (column 9: %(FP|M): 10 out of 23) until year 2021. Amongst the women of cohort 2000, 40% became full professors (column 10: %(PF|W): 4 out of 10) until year 2021. The proportion of women of those of cohort 2000 who remained AP until 2021 is 32% (column 12: %(W|AP)). The proportion of women of those of cohort 2000 who became full professor until 2021 is 29% (column 13: %(W|FP)).

The odds of becoming a full professor for cohort 2000 is 0.77 for men (Column 14: Odds(PF|M): 43%/57%, or 10/13, in rounded numbers) and 0.67 for women (column 15: Odds(PF|W): 40%/60%, or 2/3, in rounded numbers).

Finally, the odds ratio compares the odds of becoming a full professor for women to the odds of becoming a full professor for men. It can be calculated as follows:

$$OR = \frac{FP_W / AP_W}{FP_M / AP_M}$$

An odds ratio of 1 represents absolute gender parity. An odd ratio below 1 represents higher chances for men, while an odds ratio higher than 1 represents higher chances for women.

0.66) at least, a policy of ‘*repyramidage*,’ consisting of internally promoting AP to FP, has been implemented. This ratio has been stagnating at 0.40 from 2000 to 2020 in sociology in France.

The odds ratio is 0.87 for cohort 2000 (column 16). This implies that women of cohort 2000 have had 0.87 times the chance of men of becoming a full professor (until 2021).

The second-to-last line of Table 1 shows that between years 2000 and 2020, 658 AP in sociology were recruited at French universities, for whom we dispose of full career profiles until 2021 (i.e. they did not leave their status of permanent academic staff (“*enseignant-chercheur*”) at a French university under MESRI supervision until 2021). 53% of the recruited AP were female. Amongst these 658 individuals, we observe 110 transitions to full professorship until year 2021. 69 were male and 41 were female.

Due to the relatively low number of individuals for each cohort, the cohort-specific odds ratios (last column of Table 1) show high fluctuations from cohort to cohort, with odds ratios ranging from almost 0 (cohorts 2012 and 2008) to 1.23 (cohort 2006). Table 1 also illustrates that from cohort 2010 on, there are only very few transitions to full professors until year 2021, pointing to a general length of service as assistant professor before becoming full professor that exceeds 10 years for sociologists in France. These limitations render a cohort-specific approach infeasible for our empirical analysis and underscore the need to employ event-history models that permit the pooling of cohorts while simultaneously accounting for differences in their observed exposure periods.

[Figure 1 about here]

Figure 1 presents survival curves of being an associate professor for men and women, based on the whole sample of cohorts 2000 to 2020 observed until year 2021. The survival function was estimated with the Kaplan-Meier estimator for non-parametric estimation from incomplete observations (Kaplan and Meier, 1958). While 10 years after first recruitment as assistant professor, more than 90% of individuals in our sample are still assistant professors, both amongst men and women, the gender gap is quite important twenty years after first recruitment: Almost 80% of women have remained assistant professors in our sample, while this is the case for less than 60% of men, indicating that men have about twice the chances of women to become full professors, overall in our sample.

The large gender gap observed at the higher years (15 to 20 years after recruitment as assistant professor) is driven by construction by the oldest cohorts (2000 to 2004), as we dispose only for these cohorts such long time series. However, the cohort-specific odds ratios presented in table 2 do *not* suggest that there exists a clear decreasing trend in odds ratios for younger cohorts, at least not until cohort 2009. To compensate for missing insights on transitions to full professorship of more recent cohorts, section 6.5. includes a discussion of the recent evolution of annual gender ratios at recruitment of assistant and full professors (cross-sectional approach) in sociology/demography in France.

Further estimations indicate that there is no important gender-difference in the timing of transition to full professor for those who become full professors¹⁹. This is also confirmed by the descriptive findings presented in Table 2.

[Table 2 around here]

Table 2 shows the profiles of assistant professors in sociology in France who have become full professors in our sample, observed at the year they became full professors, separately for men (N=69) and women (N=41). By the time they became full professors, on average 10 years have passed since

¹⁹ Estimated interactions between *gender* and *years since recruitment* are all insignificant. Estimations with and without the interaction term yield almost identical survival curves. Estimation results with interactions are available on request.

their first recruitment as assistant professor in sociology at a French university, both for men and for women: both have been recruited as assistant professor at age 36 on average and have become full professors at age 46 on average.

Table 2 further shows that gender differences are negligible and insignificant also when it comes to the scientific profiles of newly recruited full professors: both men and women have published an average of 14 scientific articles (around 1 top article, 7 classified and 7 non-classified articles, 9 articles as sole author, 1 English article), two to three books and one of them as sole author, and one edited volume.

Similar profiles of men and women are also confirmed for high-level merits and administrative responsibilities. Our focus on 'high-level'- distinctions and responsibilities explains the low absolute number of cumulative years that we obtain on average. Women seem to have obtained slightly more ANR grants and scientific excellence - 'delegations' (Labex, IUF, CNRS...) than their male counterparts, while men have received slightly more ERC grants and CNRS medals on average, but the gender difference is always insignificant. None of the individuals, for whom we observe a transition to full professor in our sample, have figured as university president or vice-president during their years as AP. Men have figured slightly more than women as head of research center and head of department during their years as AP before their transition to full professor, but here again, none of the gender differences are significant.

While the average number of published articles and books is quite similar for men and women, this is less the case for scientific distinctions and administrative responsibilities. Gender differences may be insignificant for distinctions and administrative responsibilities mainly due to relatively large standard deviations from the mean. At the same time, we also find quite large standard deviations from the mean for published articles and books for each sex. This indicates that many individuals in our sample have published much more or much less than the average numbers. For classified articles (AERES), for example, the range goes from 0 to 31 articles. For top articles (16 journals), the range goes from 0 to 6, with more than half of the individuals in our sample having 0 articles published in one of the 16 top-journals at the time of their transition to full professor. The percentage of women having published in top journals is 54%, while it amounts to only 42% for men.

Overall however, Table 2 illustrates very similar quantitative average profiles of male and female sociologists who just became full professor in France. The average time period between the first recruitment as assistant professor and a full professorship is *not* longer for women in sociology in France, nor is their age at first recruitment as AP higher than the one of their male colleagues. Also, upon receiving full professorship, women do *not* publish more, or less, than their male colleagues on average our sample.

Gender differences in the profiles are also negligible at the earlier career stage, at recruitment as assistant professor, in sociology in France. Table B in the appendix shows the profiles of sociologists at French universities in our sample, at the year they became assistant professors, separately for men and women. Both men and women become assistant professors on average around ages 35 to 36, with an average of 4 published articles, two of which are in journals classified by AERES and three of which are written as sole author. The only significant gender difference is found for books published as sole author, with men having published somewhat more books than women.

In addition, Table B shows that one out of five assistant professors is recruited (1st affiliation) by a university in or close to Paris for men, and one out of four for women. Amongst those who become full professors in our sample, one out of four have started their career as assistant professors in or close to Paris for men; and one out of three for women (Table 2). It seems thus that starting the academic career as assistant professor at a university establishment that is situated in or close to Paris favors the transition to full professorship. Empirical analysis will show if this holds in particular for women, once we control for scientific production.

Finally, we investigate cohort effects on the sample of assistant professors²⁰. As illustrated by Figure B in the appendix, the average number of published articles observed at the year of recruitment as assistant professor increases constantly from cohort 2000 to 2020, from around 3 to around 7 publications, without considerable overall gender differences in the trend. This is driven by increases in articles published as a sole author (a doubling from 2 to 4 on average), as well as AERES-classified articles (from 1,5 to 2,5 on average). English articles and articles published in our list of 16 top-journals remain the minority even among more recent cohorts of freshly recruited assistant professors, albeit a slight increase over cohorts. Figure B shows in addition that the average number of books is rather constant over cohorts, again without any considerable gender gaps. Age at recruitment is also very constant over cohorts, around the average of 35/36, for both men and women. There are also no considerable differences between cohorts in the percentage of recruitments in/close to Paris (numbers available on request).

Last but not least, as shown in table 1 (11th column: %W), the percentage of women recruited as assistant professors in sociology in France is quite constant over cohorts 2000 to 2020, and oscillates around 50%²¹.

6. Estimation results

6.1. *The unconditional hazard of becoming full professor*

Table 3 presents the results of nested Cox regressions which estimate the factors that increase or decrease the overall hazard of becoming full professor. Hazard ratios are displayed, which implies that an effect is positive if the hazard ratio is above 1, and negative if below 1.

[Table 3 around here]

Models 1 and 2 in Table 3 are baseline models. Model 1 includes only sex, while Model 2 adds age at recruitment as assistant professor and year-fixed effects. Models 3 and 4 add publication measures. While Model 3 only controls for two basic quantitative measures of articles and books, Model 4 includes more qualitative measures for both articles and books. Model 5 adds outstanding scientific awards and Model 6 adds outstanding administrative responsibilities. Finally, model 7 adds a control for being situated in or close to Paris at the first position as assistant professors, as well as controls for secondment and inactivity.

As can be seen from Model 1, the estimated hazard ratio of becoming a full professor for women in our sample is 0.48: Overall in our sample, women have about half the chances of men to become a full professor. This hazard ratio stays almost unchanged when adding age at recruitment as assistant professor and year-fixed effects, as shown in Model 2. Note that year-fixed effects (not shown here but available on request), show an inverse U-shaped form with a peak at 10 years after first recruitment as AP, indicating that chances of becoming full professor first increase and then re-decrease over time.

Model 3 shows that articles and books have a significant positive effect in terms of becoming a full professor. Each additional article increases the chances by a factor of 1.069, that is by 7%. Each additional book boosts the chances by a factor of 1.113, that is 11%. Books thus have stronger effects than articles, but this statement must be put into perspective given that the time investment is not the same for the two outputs. The ascriptive variable ‘female’ weakens (i.e. the hazard ratio gets closer to 1) when adding scientific production, but not enough to become insignificant. An estimated coefficient

²⁰ This is possible due to sufficient sample size (N=658) and relatively equal distribution amongst cohorts, which is not the case for the subsample of those who became full professors (N=110), see Table 2.

²¹ The percentage of women applying for AP-positions in sociology in France is also quite constant and has been oscillating around 50% over the last decade (see conclusion for more details).

of 0.614 indicates that among men and women with the same overall number of articles and books, women have a 39% lower chance of getting full professor. This is a significant gender gap.

Model 4 tests whether adding more qualitative information about scientific production alters this result. With an estimated coefficient of 0.63, the gender difference remains large and significant once we control for various types of articles and books, albeit a slight decrease in the gender gap: among men and women with the same number *and type* of articles and books, women still have a 37% lower chance of getting full professor.

Amongst the articles, top articles (16 journals) and classified articles (AERES-list) have the most important impacts on the chances of becoming full professor. An additional top-article boosts the chances by almost 50%, which is considerable, and the impact of an additional classified article amounts to 16%. Amongst books, edited volumes and textbooks turn out to be significantly positively associated with becoming a full professor (changes are increased by 34% for each additional textbook and by 17.5% for each additional edited volume). In addition, once we control for the number and types of scientific production, age at recruitment as assistant professor becomes positively associated with becoming a full professor. An additional year increases the chances by 6%, suggesting the existence of some sort of 'seniority premia'.

The gender difference is little altered once we control for outstanding scientific awards, as shown by Model 5. The fact that the awards are themselves insignificant once scientific productivity is controlled for suggests that on average for men and women combined, the individual reputation generated through academic awards does not go beyond actual scientific productivity.

Model 6 adds administrative responsibility in terms of head of department and head of research unit to the explicative variables²². This reduces the gender difference to some extent, but the gap remains significant. With the female-coefficient being at 0.645, women now have around 40% lower chances than men of becoming full professors, scientific production *and* administrative top-responsibilities controlled for. Table 3 has indeed shown that men who just became full professors have figured more than women as directors of departments and of research labs during their years of assistant professors. The gender difference was not significant, but this is likely to be mainly caused by sample size²³. This points to the importance of controlling for administrative responsibilities when analyzing determinants of academic careers and its gender bias in sociology in France. As it cannot be excluded that women are overrepresented in lower-level administrative responsibilities (direction of a Master or undergraduate diploma, for example, or other pedagogic missions such as for example for exchange programs), missing information about these tasks is regrettable. Model 6 has shown that once we control for scientific productivity, high-level administrative responsibilities in terms of being the head of a research department do indeed increase the chances of becoming full professor. Regressions by gender will show if there exists a gender-specific compensation for high-level administrative tasks once we control for scientific productivity.

Overall, Models 1 to 6 suggest that the gender gap in the chances of becoming a full professor is somewhat reduced (from 50% to 40%) once scientific production and high-level administrative responsibilities are controlled for, but remains significant.

Model 7 adds the Paris-location as well as secondment and inactivity to the explicative variables. This reduces the estimated female-coefficient, and therewith re-widens the significant gender gap: women are now found to have only 0.56 times the chances than men to become a full professor. This suggests that the Paris-location may be more favorable for men than for women, once academic merit is controlled for, as it will be investigated in gender-specific regressions in the following. Besides, adding location to the estimation model reinforces the importance of publications of articles in top-journals and of

²² President or vice-president were dropped from the regression as no transition to full professorship has been observed for those who have had these responsibilities during their years of assistant professor.

Overall in the sample, there are 0 individuals having been university president over the observed period, 5 vice residents, 12 directors of research units, and 21 department directors.

²³ Amongst those who became full professors, 7 men and 2 women were research unit-directors as assistant professors. 6 men and 1 women were department directors.

textbooks. This suggests that the impact of publishing in top journals and of textbooks is not the same for those located in Paris and those located in the rest of France²⁴.

Both men and women combined, Model 7 shows a highly significant and large coefficient for being employed by a university in or close to Paris at first employment as assistant professor. The coefficient is, with 1.79 the largest estimated coefficient amongst all. This implies that, once we control for scientific productivity and top-level administrative responsibilities, assistant professors who start their career at universities in or close to Paris have almost two times the chances of becoming full professors. Note that location should not fully capture scientific productivity, as it is controlled for in Model 7. The high coefficient should therefore be caused by other, non-observed factors, such as for example a much higher number of job offers and/or network and mobility effects in and around Paris.

Finally, Model 7 shows that assistant professors with temporary absences due to secondment in our sample have significantly lower chances of becoming full professor in sociology at a French university.

Considering Model 7 as our most complete model, we conclude that everything else held constant, location is the most impactful determinant for becoming a full professor. The second most important determinant is being male (we obtain a HR of 1.65 for male when switching the gender variable from female to male in model 7), followed by articles in top-journals and textbooks. Having been the head of a research unit as well as having published classified articles and edited volumes also emerge as favoring transitions to full professorship, but to a lower extent.

[Table 4 around here]

Table 4 shows results of Cox regressions on the overall hazard of becoming full professor by gender, focusing on the full specification (Model 7 in Table 3), and revealing several significant differences between men and women in the determinants of becoming full professor. Note that overall, scientific production as measured by the cumulated number of articles as well as the cumulated number of books does not emerge as more important for women than for men²⁵. However, we find significant gender differences for certain specific outputs such as for English books, articles as a sole author and English articles. Top articles are highly significant for both men and women and the gender difference is insignificant. Once controlled for top-articles, other articles emerge as significantly more important for men than for women. Aside from significance, Table 4 suggests that articles and books as sole author, English articles and books, edited volumes and textbooks are more important for women than for men. It is possible that this is due to a “signaling effect” of autonomous productivity that is stronger for women.

This is in line with the significant difference between men and women that is found for ‘delegations’ labelled as ‘scientific excellence’ such as those granted by LABEX, IUF or CNRS, which are positive predictors for women only. It is possible that the positive coefficient for women only is due to a signaling effect that women need more than men to become full professors. At the same time, it is important to consider that these delegations are often granted for research projects that include the preparation of a ‘*habilitation à diriger des recherches (HDR)*’ and come with a reduction in the teaching load (50% to 100%). Especially for time-constrained mothers of young children, the delegations may not only increase

²⁴ Regressions including an interaction between the Paris-location and publications in top-journals yield an interaction term which is significant at 10% ($p=0.051$). Publishing in top-journals is thus more rewarding for assistant professors located in Paris (HR 1.9 in Paris and 1.3 outside Paris). Eventually, for recruitments outside Paris, other merits such as administrative tasks are also important. Note however that in regressions with interactions, we find that all other differences in hazard ratios between assistant professors located in and outside Paris are insignificant (including gender). Results available on request.

²⁵ Estimating Model 3 by gender reveals that the differences between women and men for the overall cumulated number of articles as well as for the overall cumulated number of books are not significant (results available on request).

overall scientific productivity, but also and in particular the chances of writing and defending a HDR (which is a pre-requisite for the application process, as detailed in section 3).

Table 4 shows moreover that having directed a research unit is predictive for becoming a full professor for men more than for women. The gender difference is albeit not significant. However, this is most likely due to sample size issues. Thus, it cannot be fully excluded that the compensation for high-level administrative tasks is somewhat stronger for men than for women, all other things being equal.

Finally, for both men and women, being located in or close to Paris at first recruitment as assistant professor emerges as the strongest predictor for both men and women - publications, awards and administrative tasks being controlled for. For women, however, the estimated hazard ratio is insignificant, as is the gender difference in hazard ratios. The fact that the estimated hazard ratio of the Paris-location is very high for both men and women suggests nevertheless that for both sexes, location is an important factor for the transition to full professors, besides merit-based aspects.

Table C in the appendix provides more detailed information about location by showing how those who became full professors are distributed over different categories combining university affiliation at 1st recruitment as assistant professors and at 1st recruitment as full professor.

Amongst the 110 full professors in our sample, 46% did not change university affiliation when becoming a full professor (internal recruitment rate: 45% for men and 49% for women). Amongst those who started their career as assistant professors in/around Paris, the overall percentage is, with 41%, somewhat lower than the average, but the gender difference is higher (internal recruitment rate for assistant professors in/around Paris: 35% for men and 50% for women).²⁶ Thus, while internal and external recruitments balance out for women independent of their first location as assistant professors, it seems that for men, the Paris-location facilitates becoming a full professor at a university that is different from the one they started at as assistant professor.

However, amongst male professors who started their career as assistant professor in/around Paris and changed affiliation as full professor, the large majority became professors outside Paris (9 out of 11). For their female counterparts, the opposite is the case. The large majority of women who have started as assistant professors in/around Paris and changed affiliation as full professors have nevertheless remained in Paris (5 out of 6).

Overall (internal and external recruitments combined), the majority of professors who started as assistant professors in/around Paris remain in/around Paris. This is true for both sexes (8/17 for men and 11/12 for women; both sexes combined: 66%). If we also consider universities in the larger region around Paris (“Ile de France”) for professors (as for example universities in Cergy, Evry, Versailles, Marne la Vallée), this figure amounts to 86%. The figure even amounts to 90% if we consider universities in “*Ile de France*” for *both* assistant professors and full professors. Only 4 out of 41 full professors who have started their career as assistant professors in Paris or Ile de France have become professors outside Paris/Ile de France. And only 6 out of 69 professors who have started their career as assistant professors outside Ile de France have become professors in Paris or Ile de France (9%).

To sum up, the Paris location importantly favors transition to full professors for both sexes. It seems that for men, the Paris location facilitates an institutional change, be it in/around Paris or elsewhere in France. For women, the Paris location enables above all remaining in/around Paris.

The last step of our analysis of the unconditional hazard of becoming a professor consists in providing two important robustness checks. The first robustness check is for exits, and the second robustness check is for transitions to full professorship outside the domain of sociology/demography (section 19).

Table D in the appendix provides regression results of an alternative empirical analysis allowing us to treat exits of associate professors as a distinct event besides the transition from associate to full professor. Results of these logistic discrete-time hazard models for multiple absorbing events models (mlogit),

²⁶ No change of university affiliation for those who started their career as AP outside Paris: internal recruitment rate for men 48%, for women 48%, overall 48%.

which estimate a separate discrete-time hazard for each type of absorbing event (becoming full professor, exiting the academic sector without re-entry due to retirement, death, career change), confirm the robustness of our results for transitions to full professor. The estimated female odds ratios of becoming a full professor remain significant in all specifications and confirm that women's chances of becoming full professor are almost reduced by half in comparison to men, even when controlling for scientific productivity and other merits. The female odds ratios of exiting the academic sector are always insignificant, but the odds are considerably higher for women in comparison to men when the scientific profile is controlled for (low significance might be caused by low sample size). The significance of age at recruitment as assistant professor for exits might be related to retirement, while the importance of top articles for exits might be related to job market opportunities abroad or in academic positions outside the public sector. Secondment and inactivity are also strong predictors for exits.

Table E in the appendix provides regression results focusing on transitions to full professorship in sociology/demography only (section 19). The first three columns show the results of an empirical setup in which only transitions within section 19 are coded as successful transitions (98 amongst the 110 transitions), while the remaining 12 individuals who became full professors in other disciplines are kept in the database and considered as 'unsuccessful'. The last three columns provide results of an alternative setup in which the 12 individuals are entirely dropped out of the database. Both setups confirm the robustness of our findings by indicating highly significant female hazard ratios. Both specifications with controls indicate that independent of meritocratic factors, women who start their career as assistant professors in sociology/demography have almost only half the chances compared to their male counterparts of becoming a full professor in the same academic sector in France. Mlogit regression treating the two types of transition as separate events (to full professorship within vs. outside section 19) confirm these findings and are available on request.

Overall, the results presented in this section show that in our overall sample of assistant professors hired between years 2000 and 2020 in section 19 in France, who are all considered as potential candidates for full professorship, there exists a substantial promotion gap between men and women. This gap remains large once we control for co-variables such as age and productivity.

6.2. *The hazard of applying for qualification*

The limitation of our analysis so far is that we do not know whether the gender gap in observed transitions to full professorship are the result of lower success rates of women or the result of a lower propensity of women to apply for promotion to full professor. We therefore decompose the different career steps between first recruitment as assistant professor and first recruitment as full professor in the following and examine each step separately. We start by considering the application for qualification as first observable entry into competition. Candidates are admitted to apply for the qualification if they have completed and successfully defended their habilitation thesis ("*habilitation à diriger des recherches*": HDR). The HDR criteria is unobserved in our data base, but may be covered -at least in parts- by the observed publication record. Note that all qualification candidates certainly hold a HDR, but not everyone who holds a HDR stands as a qualification candidate. Once the candidates obtain the qualification, they are formally entitled to apply for full professor positions in section 19 for a period of four years.

[Table 5 around here]

Table 5 shows Cox regression results on the hazard of applying for qualification in section 19.

The baseline Model 1 shows that the estimated hazard ratio of applying for qualification for women is 0.55, which implies that overall in our sample of assistant professors, women have only about half the chances of men to enter the competition for full professorship. The gender gap is, however, reduced to a considerable extent, once scientific productivity and other co-variables are controlled for. This reduction

suggest that the gender gap that we find for the overall hazard of becoming full professor gender gap stems at least in parts from a gender gap in academic productivity.

All things being equal, the estimated female hazard ratio of 0.72 is nevertheless significant at a 10% level. This implies that it cannot be fully excluded that women who are equally productive than men have a lower propensity to enter the competition. A part of the gender gap that we find for the overall hazard of becoming full professor is thus likely to be caused by self-selection of competitive women against competition (be it due to mobility, preferences, self-perception or anticipated discrimination).

Table 5 shows furthermore that the publication of top articles and classified articles as well as of books as sole author are important factors for entering the competition. These outputs are likely to overlap in content with a habilitation thesis. The Paris location also emerges as a very prominent factor for applying for qualification.

Table F in the appendix shows results of the full model by gender and indicates, similarly as we found for the unconditioned transition to full professorship, that when it comes to apply for qualification, delegations are more important for women, and outstanding administrative tasks are more important for men. It thus seems that delegations particularly support female academic careers, eventually they facilitate the writing of a habilitation thesis through teaching load reductions. For scientific production itself, we find no significant gender difference in the impact on the hazard of applying for qualification. The Paris location is important for both sexes, without a significant gender gap. The insignificant interaction between gender and location also indicates that the application gap between men and women is not significantly different between the region in/around Paris and the rest of France.

6.3. The hazard of becoming qualified conditioned on applying for qualification

We now analyze differences in the hazard of becoming qualified in section 19 conditioned on applying for qualification in section 19. Table 6 reports results for this hazard and indicates that the conditional hazard of becoming qualified is not significantly different between women and men. The estimated baseline hazard ratio for women is 0.92. Adding co-variates decreases women's hazard ratio slightly, but the estimated coefficient (0.89) remains insignificant. The gender gap that we find for the overall hazard of becoming full professor is thus unlikely to stem in important parts from a gender bias in the granting of the qualification. Table 6 also shows that the large majority of individuals who have ever applied for qualification in our sample are observed to obtain the qualification within the observed time framework (until year 2021).

[Table 6 around here]

Table 6 reports furthermore that all things being equal (including scientific production), candidates who started their career in and around Paris have a significantly higher hazard of becoming qualified. This could be due to non-observed factors like for example network effects and/or the scientific prestige of Parisian universities which may procure additional signaling effects beyond scientific productivity. Having published edited volumes and textbooks also increases the hazard of obtaining qualification to a considerable extent.

Table G in the appendix shows results of the full model by gender. The results indicate a strong gender difference in the impact of delegations on the conditional hazard of becoming qualified, with a positive coefficient for women and a negative coefficient for men. This suggest that besides freeing up time that can be devoted to a habilitation thesis, delegations may also create strong signaling effects for women.

6.4. The hazard of applying for full professorship conditioned on being qualified

We turn next to the hazard of applying for full professorship in section 19 conditioned on being qualified in section 19. Table 7 reports the results for this hazard and indicates that the large majority of individuals who ever became qualified in our sample are observed to apply for full professorship within the observed time framework (144 subjects and 135 failures both men and women combined: 94%).

[Table 7 around here]

The estimated gender difference in the conditioned hazard of applying for full professorship is insignificant, even if -all things being equal- women are only 81% as likely as men to apply. This could stem amongst other things from women's lower mobility. Table H in the appendix reports gender differences in the conditioned hazard of applying for full professorship. A strong publication record in terms of books as well as having had a delegation seem to encourage women more than men to apply.

6.5. The hazard of becoming full professor conditioned on applying for full professorship.

We now analyze the final stage of promotion by estimating the hazard of becoming full professor in section 19 conditioned on applying for full professorship in section 19. Table 8 presents the results. While women's raw hazard ratio is relatively close to 1 and insignificant (Model 1), the hazard ratio gets smaller and becomes significant at the 10% level once we control for our usual set of co-variables (Model 3). This indicates that amongst candidates with similar scientific profiles, women have only 65% of chances of men of being promoted as full professor. This gender gap is considerable. Regression results of Model 3 also suggest that amongst the overall pool of candidates, scientific production is no longer importantly related with the hazard of promotion. Only two out of ten variables related to scientific production show significantly positive coefficients (classified articles, textbooks). The criteria that is the most positively related with promotion is again the Paris location. Gender is the second most important criteria (hazard ratio for men: 1.55).

[Table 8]

To get a better understanding of the important gender gap in conditional promotion, we now add information on the application behavior of candidates. It could be that women apply for fewer positions, and in particular for fewer outside positions, compared to men, which may reduce their hazard of promotion. This could be caused by stronger mobility restrictions for women, which may be particularly pronounced for women who are situated outside Paris.

In a first step, we integrate the cumulated number of applications into the estimation model (Model 4).

A first descriptive snapshot based on our longitudinal data (figures not illustrated) shows that amongst the overall pool of 135 candidates, women do not send out significantly fewer applications than men (4.8 applications for women, and 4.4 applications for men on average for cohorts 2000 to 2020). There is also no considerable gender gap in the number of applications when comparing only successful or only unsuccessful candidates, neither when comparing only candidates inside or only outside Paris. Figure D confirms the absence of gender-specific patterns in the number of applications when applying a complementary cross-sectional perspective for calendar years 2009 to 2023, both for assistant professor positions as well as for full professor positions in sociology/demography in France.

Regression results of Model 4 confirm that fewer applications amongst women are not the main driver of the gender gap in promotions. The number of applications is positively related with the hazard of becoming full professor, and as are most items of scientific publication now that we control for the number of applications. Thus, amongst candidates with an equal number of applications, more productive candidates do have higher chances of becoming full professor. However, adding this control increases woman's hazard ratio of becoming full professor only slightly (to 0.65), and the gender gap remains significant at the 10% level. Thus, a stronger overall limitation of applications amongst female candidates does not figure as main explanation of the gender gap in promotions.

In a second step, we integrate a dummy variable into the estimation model which equals 1 if candidates have ever applied for outside positions (Model 5). It is possible that even if women do not apply less on average, they wait longer until internal positions open and focus more on internal positions when applying. Amongst the unsuccessful candidates, we observe indeed that a quarter of unsuccessful women have applied only internally, whereas only 5% of unsuccessful men have applied only internally. Model 5 confirms that once we control for outside applications, the female hazard ratio of becoming full professor increases and becomes insignificant. The estimated coefficient for the dummy of outside applications indicates fewer chances for promotion for external candidates in comparison to internal candidates. However, with a female hazard ratio estimated at 0.7 and a p-value of 0.18, and given the sample size and structure, we consider that discriminatory mechanisms cannot be fully excluded when it comes to the recruitment procedure of full professors.

Regression results of Model 5 by gender, presented in Table I in the appendix, indicate that external recruitments are even more difficult for women than they are for men. What favors women's overall promotion chances more than men's, once differences in applications are controlled for, is age and articles as sole author.

Finally, we distinguish in our empirical analysis between internal and external promotions. Results are presented in Table 9. The regression estimating the hazard of becoming full professor at the same university (internal recruitment) indicates a female hazard ratio of 1.2 when controls are included (full specification as in Model 5, Table 8, i.e. number and type of applications are controlled for: Model 2 in Table 9), which is insignificant. This suggests that discriminatory mechanisms can be excluded for internal recruitment.

The regression estimating the hazard of becoming full professor at a different university (external recruitment) indicates a female hazard ratio of 0.48 (with controls, Model 4 in Table 9), which is significant at the 10% level ($p=0.088$). The hazard ratio remains unchanged when we replace the dummy variable for external applications by a continuous variable indicating the cumulative number of external applications (result available on request). We do not control for the spatial distribution of external applications, which could be wider for men than for women. However, the low and robust female hazard ratio suggests that discrimination remains a potential causal mechanism when it comes to explain the gender gap in external recruitments.

Table 9 further suggests that scientific production is taken into consideration more for external than for internal recruitment. The Paris location is important for both types of promotion, not only for external recruitment. Further regressions by gender show that the importance of the Paris location is not significantly different for men and for women, be it for internal or for external recruitments (results available on request). This suggests that the Paris location offers other advantages besides mobility, such as a high number of open positions, for example²⁷.

To provide further insights in the recruitment process, we complement once again our longitudinal analysis with descriptive insights based on cross-sectional data for calendar years 2000 to 2020. Figure E in the appendix illustrates for both assistant professors (Figure E.1) and full professors (Figure E.2) the percentage and odds of women at recruitment (left y-axis), as well as two different odds ratios at recruitment (right y-axis): one odds ratio based on the number of candidates and one odds ratio based

²⁷ 40% of full professors who have been recruited between the years 2009 and 2023 have been recruited at universities situated in/around Paris in section 19.

on the number of applications. For assistant professors, all numbers have been oscillating since 2000 around the black bar which indicates gender parity (with relatively high yearly fluctuations nevertheless). On average over the observed time period, 53% of recruited assistant professors have been women. For recruited full professors, on average only 36% have been women, but the percentage has been constantly somewhat above 50% since the year 2019 (i.e. since relatively recently). In addition, for full professors, the odds ratios indicate that since 2013, women have somewhat higher chances than men to be recruited, given that there are fewer female than male candidates. The odds ratio for applications is only since the year 2019 somewhat, but not considerably lower than the odds ratio for candidates.

These descriptive insights strengthen our assumption that differences in the application behavior between men and women cannot fully explain why in our empirical analysis based on cohorts 2000 to 2020, we find a considerable gender gap in external recruitments of full professors when comparing candidates with similar publication profiles.

7. Decomposition analysis

In this final step, we identify the contribution of each stage of promotion to the overall gender gap in promotion. It may well be that the gender gap that we identified in the last stage of promotion, i.e. the recruitment of full professors, does not weight much in the overall gender gap that we identified in section 6.1.

To get an idea about the importance of each step of the promotion for the overall gender gap, we decompose the estimated overall hazard of becoming a full professor in section 19 for men and women into the estimated unconditioned hazards of the three previous promotion steps: applying for qualification, becoming qualified and applying for full professorship.

Table J in the appendix shows the estimated baseline hazards for men and women in our sample²⁸. The last line indicates that in our sample, 39.95% of men and 22.63% of women became full professors. This implies a gender gap in the overall promotion of 43.35%, which represents the full gender gap (set at 100% in the fourth column). The fifth column shows the contribution of each step in the promotion to the overall promotion gap: 74.30% stem from the first step, i.e. applying for qualification in section 19. The following two steps, i.e. becoming qualified and applying for full professorship, contribute only to a small extent to the gender gap (0.6% and 3.6% respectively). The remaining 21.56% can then be attributed to the last promotion step, which is the final recruitment amongst the pool of candidates.

About three quarters of the overall gender gap in promotion can thus be explained by fewer women applying for qualification, and almost one quarter by fewer female candidates being recruited as full professors.

In our sample, women have only about half the chances of men of applying for qualification (estimated baseline hazard ratio 0.55, Table 5), which can stem from the fact that women are less productive in scientific terms as assistant professors. We observe indeed important productivity gap between men and women that cumulate with the years, as illustrated in Figure C in the appendix. The most important gender gap is for the number of books published as sole author, which eventually includes habilitation theses. However, once we controlled for scientific publications, our estimated female hazard ratio remained, with 0.7., significant and important. This indicates that amongst equally productive assistant professors, women apply less for qualification than men. They might be less inclined to write a (time-consuming) habilitation theses besides scientific production, but they also can be less inclined to enter the competition (which can be due to restricted mobility, differences in preferences and self-perception, and and/or anticipated discrimination at the final recruitment stage).

²⁸ Numbers based on cox proportional hazard regressions with sex as only independent variable: 1-survival rate as assistant professor observed 20 years after first recruitment as assistant professor.

For the final recruitment stage as full professors, we observe that qualified women are not less likely than qualified men to enter competition, but they apply less for external positions. However, once we control for external applications, the female hazard ratio of becoming full professor remains, again with 0.7, relatively important. It thus cannot be fully excluded that discriminatory mechanisms are at play at this final stage, in particular for external recruitments.

8. Conclusion

8.1. Summary of results

In this article, we have analyzed gender differences in academic career patterns among sociologists in France. We therefore used event-history models based on a unique panel dataset that covers the full career profiles of all sociologists who were recruited as assistant professors (“maîtres de conférences”) between 2000 and 2020 at French universities.

The dataset includes two major new features. First, we use non-anonymous data containing all individuals appointed as assistant professors (AP) and full professors (FP) in a given year at a French university. These data come from the administrative records of the Human Resources Directorate (DGRH) of the French Ministry of Higher Education and Research (MESRI), as well as from individual-level data on applications and recruitments for academic positions, also provided by MESRI. Second, for all individuals recruited as APs in sociology between 2000 and 2020, we have collected and coded yearly information on scientific production (articles and books), administrative responsibilities, as well as awards and grants.

As our dataset covers the full career profiles of all APs in sociology in France employed since 2000, we were able to apply event-history models to estimate the different hazards of promotion from assistant to full professor. We analyzed the overall hazard of becoming a full professor, as well as four more specific hazards: applying for qualification; becoming qualified conditional on applying for qualification; applying for full professorship conditional on being qualified; and becoming a full professor conditional on applying for full professorship.

Our results indicate that, among those recruited as assistant professors between 2000 and 2020, women have had only about half the chances of men to become full professors by 2021. The gender gap in the chances of becoming a full professor is somewhat reduced (to about 40%) once scientific production and high-level administrative responsibilities are controlled for, but it remains significant. When scientific productivity and other merits are held constant, being male remains the second most impactful determinant of becoming a full professor in sociology/demography in France, after being located at a Parisian university as an assistant professor.

The Paris location facilitates the transition to full professorship for both men and women, suggesting important network and mobility effects. Merits that signal scientific excellence beyond scientific publication, such as sole-authored publications, publications in English, or research delegations, emerge as particularly important for women, suggesting that women still need to “signal” autonomous and outstanding productivity.

When decomposing the different career steps between first recruitment as assistant professor and first recruitment as full professor, we find that women have had only about half the chances of men to apply for qualification (a career step that requires writing and defending a habilitation (HDR) and is necessary in order to enter competition). The gender gap in entering the competition is, however, reduced to some extent (estimated female hazard ratio: 0.72) once scientific productivity and other covariates are controlled for. As the gap remains nevertheless considerable and significant at the 10% level, it cannot be fully excluded that women who are equally productive as men have a lower propensity to enter the competition. This may be caused by gender differences in mobility, preferences, self-perception, and/or anticipated discrimination. In addition, it is likely that the habilitation process is more costly for women. This is suggested by our finding that research delegations (which imply substantial teaching load

reductions) emerge as more impactful for women than for men when it comes to the chances of applying for qualification, everything else held constant.

Once having applied for qualification, we find that the differences between men and women in the chances of becoming qualified are insignificant, as are the differences in the chances of applying for full professorship conditional on being qualified.

When estimating the chances of becoming a full professor conditional on applying for full professorship, however, we find that, all else being equal, women have only 65% of men's chances of being promoted to full professor. Gender again emerges as the second most important recruitment criterion, after the Paris location. The gender gap remains considerable once we account for gender differences in the number of internal and external applications, and external recruitments emerge as significantly more difficult for women than for men compared to internal recruitments. This leads us to conclude that discriminatory mechanisms cannot be fully excluded in the recruitment procedure for full professors.

When identifying the contribution of each stage of promotion to the overall gender gap in promotion, we find that the overall gender gap in promotion from assistant professor to full professor in sociology/demography in France is caused by about three quarters by the gender gap in applying for qualification, that is, the gender gap in entering competition. The gender gap in entering competition is itself mainly caused, with about two thirds, by differences in scientific production between men and women. However, about one third of the gender gap in qualification remains unexplained, suggesting that there are competitive women who do not apply for qualification (and/or do not write a habilitation). About one quarter of the overall gender gap in promotion can be attributed to the final recruitment process. For this final recruitment stage, we find that qualified women are not less likely than qualified men to enter competition, but they apply less for external positions. However, the gender gap in external recruitments remains substantial once we control for gender differences in the number and spatial distribution of applications.

8.2. Discussion and outlook

Several important policy implications emerge from these findings: two concern the qualification procedure, and the third concerns the final recruitment process.

First and foremost, women publish on average less than men during their first years as assistant professors and this explains the majority of the gender gap in promotion to full professor in sociology/demography in France. Even if unobserved in our analysis, it is highly likely that this is mainly due to family responsibilities (Stack 2004, Zheng 2022). At French universities, some measures exist that aim to facilitate the scientific productivity of female assistant professors with children. Primarily, mothers benefit from a 50% teaching load reduction shortly after childbirth, during the academic year that follows the maternity leave period of 16 weeks. In addition, when applying for research delegations and grants for junior researchers, the age limit is extended by six months per child for women with children. Given the considerable gender gap in publications, however, it seems evident that these measures are far from sufficient to facilitate an academic career for young mothers.

Second, there are women who are equally productive as their male colleagues but do not enter competition for full professor positions. One of the factors behind this phenomenon (besides self-perception, mobility, work-task considerations, and the anticipation of discriminatory mechanisms at the final stage of recruitment) may be the relatively complicated and time-consuming qualification procedure in France, notably the requirement of a habilitation (HDR), for which some universities require additional original research beyond existing publications. Simplifying the habilitation process, for example by placing greater emphasis on already published material, could contribute to higher transition rates to full professorship among women.

Third, as external recruitments emerge as more difficult for women than for men everything else held constant, and as our results suggest that the gender gap at the final recruitment stage cannot be explained solely by more restricted mobility for women, the mechanisms at play in the final stage of full professor

recruitment require further attention. On the one hand, it appears to be particularly important for women to have opportunities for full professorship within their own university. For the promotion of female academic careers, it is therefore crucial to maintain the possibility of internal careers and to sustain and strengthen a demographic dynamic within sociology departments that consists in not eliminating professorial positions but creating additional ones. This represents a major challenge, especially for universities outside Paris, and budget cuts should increasingly be examined from a gender perspective. On the other hand, it is important to promote women's chances in external recruitments. It is conceivable that women are not explicitly discriminated against, but are nonetheless implicitly disadvantaged. For example, an overly narrow thematic definition of job profiles may both reduce the number of female applications and disadvantage female candidates. Greater openness in defining professorial profiles could enable faculties to achieve greater gender parity in their research and teaching.

These are only some of the policy implications that can be derived directly or indirectly from our study; the list is far from exhaustive. Taken together, our findings suggest that policies aimed at reducing gender inequalities in access to full professorship should intervene early in academic careers, particularly by lowering the costs and constraints associated with qualification and mobility. Measures such as targeted support for the habilitation process, greater transparency and standardization in recruitment procedures, and enhanced monitoring of external hiring outcomes could help mitigate cumulative disadvantages faced by women. More broadly, addressing gender inequality in senior academic positions requires not only fostering individual productivity but also reforming institutional practices that structure competition and promotion.

Beyond the policy debate, our article also points to several avenues for future research on women in academic careers. These include, for example, comparisons with other disciplines in France, within and beyond the social sciences, as well as international comparisons between French sociology departments and other systems characterized by tenure tracks (such as the German or Anglo-Saxon system, for example). What is also relevant for future studies is an improvement in the measurement of academic productivity, for instance with regard to co-authorship, citations, impact factors, teaching quality, student satisfaction, and lower-level administrative responsibilities. Other important factors that remained unobserved in our study include demographic characteristics such as number of children and couple status, as well as further career indicators before and after recruitment as assistant professors, such as PhD and Master institutions, postdoctoral years, international mobility, conference participation, and media engagement. Many other important factors, such as socio-economic background, motivational factors, and family mobility constraints, and the habilitation itself, are also not observed. A holistic measurement of all possible determinants goes far beyond the scope of a quantitative assessment. We therefore believe that qualitative studies would be highly complementary.

Finally, one of the most surprising insights of our study, which remains underexplored, is the importance of the Paris location. We find that being located in Paris as assistant professor strongly favors the transition to full professorship—publications held constant and independently of gender and institutional change—and that the Paris location even favors becoming qualified among candidates for qualification. This suggests that, beyond mobility issues, network and signaling effects may play an important role in academic careers in France. Further investigation is needed to fully understand the underlying mechanisms. One may also hypothesize that better working conditions in the larger departments often located in or around Paris (fewer administrative tasks, greater research budgets) facilitate the transition to full professorship beyond their direct impact on publications, for example by freeing up time to write a habilitation. To fully capture these aspects, a qualitative analysis and/or an experimental study would be useful.

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Figures

Figure 1: Kaplan-Meier survival curves of being an assistant professor in sociology, by sex

Data source: French Ministry of Higher Education and Research (MESRI), 2022.

Sample: Complete population of individuals who were recruited as assistant professors (*“maîtres de conférences”*) in sociology/demography (CNU section 19) at French universities between years 2000 and 2020, followed through 2021.

Tables

Table 1: Transitions to full professors – cohort by cohort

Cohort	n	M.	W.	in 2021			in 2021			in 2021			Odds(FP M.)	Odds(FP W.)	Odds ratio
				FP :	M.	W.	% FP	%(FP M.)	%(FP W.)	% W.	%(W. AP)	%(W. FP)			
2000	33	23	10	14	10	4	42	43	40	30	32	29	0,77	0,67	0,87
2001	33	19	14	16	14	2	48	74	14	42	71	13	2,80	0,17	0,06
2002	32	11	21	10	4	6	31	36	29	66	68	60	0,57	0,40	0,70
2003	35	10	25	12	4	8	34	40	32	71	74	67	0,67	0,47	0,71
2004	23	13	10	9	6	3	39	46	30	43	50	33	0,86	0,43	0,50
2005	41	21	20	15	12	3	37	57	15	49	65	20	1,33	0,18	0,13
2006	36	15	21	13	5	8	36	33	38	58	57	62	0,50	0,62	1,23
2007	35	15	20	10	6	4	29	40	20	57	64	40	0,67	0,25	0,38
2008	30	15	15	2	2	0	7	13	0	50	54	0	0,15	0,00	0,00
2009	37	19	18	7	5	2	19	26	11	49	53	29	0,36	0,13	0,35
2010	40	23	17							43					
2011	30	14	16							53					
2012	42	18	24							57					
2013	28	6	22							79					
2014	32	14	18	1		1				56					
2015	21	11	10	1	1					48					
2016	31	11	20							65					
2017	25	17	8							32					
2018	22	12	10							45					
2019	29	12	17							59					
2020	23	8	15							65					
Total	658	307	351	110	69	41									
Arithmetic Mean							32	41	23	53	59	35			

Data source: French Ministry of Higher Education and Research (MESRI), 2022.

Sample: Complete population of individuals who were recruited as assistant professors (“*maîtres de conférences*”) in sociology/demography (CNU section 19) at French universities between years 2000 and 2020, followed through 2021.

Note: AP for Assistant Professor, FP for Full Professor, M. for Men, W. for Women

Table 2: Characteristics of sociologists who have become full professors, observed at the year of recruitment as full professors

	<i>Men</i>		<i>Women</i>		<i>Sig. Dif.</i>
	<i>Mean</i>	<i>(st. dev.)</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>(st. dev.)</i>	
<i>Age at recruitment as assistant professor</i>	35,84	(0,80)	35,71	(0,94)	-
<i>Age at recruitment as full professor</i>	46,19	(0,83)	45,95	(0,82)	-
<u>Cumulative number of:</u>					
<i>Articles (total)</i>	14,33	(0,94)	14,34	(1,15)	-
<i>Top articles[§]</i>	0,64	(0,12)	0,83	(0,14)	-
<i>Classified articles[§]</i>	6,74	(0,54)	7,27	(0,58)	-
<i>Other articles</i>	7,59	(0,68)	7,07	(0,89)	-
<i>Articles sole author</i>	8,93	(0,70)	9,00	(0,96)	-
<i>English articles</i>	0,83	(0,18)	0,90	(0,20)	-
<i>Books (total)</i>	2,70	(0,26)	2,44	(0,39)	-
<i>Books sole author</i>	1,39	(0,13)	1,20	(0,18)	-
<i>Books in English</i>	0,01	(0,01)	0,10	(0,06)	-
<i>Edited volumes</i>	1,25	(0,22)	1,12	(0,26)	-
<i>Textbooks</i>	0,12	(0,07)	0,27	(0,17)	-
<u>Cumulative number of years:</u>					
<i>ANR grants</i>	0,10	(0,08)	0,24	(0,12)	-
<i>ERC grants</i>	0,06	(0,06)	0,00	(/)	-
<i>CNRS chair</i>	0,09	(0,09)	0,00	(/)	-
<i>Delegation (CNRS, Labex, IUF)</i>	0,10	(0,06)	0,37	(0,19)	-
<i>Admin: university president</i>	0,00	(/)	0,00	(/)	-
<i>Admin: university vice-president</i>	0,00	(/)	0,00	(/)	-
<i>Admin: head of research center</i>	0,52	(0,22)	0,17	(0,15)	-
<i>Admin: head of department</i>	0,28	(0,14)	0,10	(0,10)	-
<u>Dummy:</u>					
<i>1st AP-position in/around Paris</i>	0,25	(0,05)	0,29	(0,07)	-
<i>Ever in secondment</i>	0,03	(0,02)	0,00	(/)	-
<i>Ever inactive</i>	0,03	(0,02)	0,02	(0,02)	-
Number of individuals	69		41		

Significant difference: + $p < 0.1$, * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$ (significance levels of two-sided tests of mean differences between men and women).

Data source: French Ministry of Higher Education and Research (MESRI), 2022.

Sample: Complete population of individuals who were recruited as assistant professors (“*maîtres de conférences*”) in sociology/demography (CNU section 19) at French universities between years 2000 and 2020 and who became full professors until 2021.

[§]flagship publications (alphabetical order): American Journal of Sociology, Annual Review of Sociology, American Sociological Review, Demography, Economie et Statistique, Espace Population et Société,

European Sociological Review, Journal of Marriage and the Family, Population, Population and Development Review, Revue Française de Sociologie, Sociological Review, Sociologie du Travail, Sociologies, Sociology, Travail Genre Société.

‡AERES lists 2008-2013.

Table 3: Cox regression on the hazard of becoming full professor (exponentiated coefficients: hazard ratios)

		1	2	3	4	5	6	7
		Gender only	Time var. added	Productivity (quant.) added	Productivity (qual.) added	Awards added	Admin. resp. added	1st AP in Paris added
Year-fixed effects		no	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes
Cumulative number of:	<i>Female</i>	0.480***	0.504***	0.614*	0.630*	0.625*	0.645*	0.558*
	<i>Age at recruitment AP</i>		1.016	1.036	1.057*	1.060**	1.062**	1.064**
	<i>Articles(total)</i>			1.069***				
	<i>Books (total)</i>			1.113*				
	<i>Top articles[§]</i>				1.458***	1.456**	1.459**	1.536**
	<i>Classified articles[£]</i>				1.164***	1.168***	1.167***	1.165***
	<i>Other articles</i>				1.049	1.051+	1.038	1.031
	<i>Articles sole author</i>				0.986	0.985	0.994	0.996
	<i>English articles</i>				0.974	0.971	0.980	1.001
	<i>Books sole author</i>				1.102	1.096	1.083	1.063
	<i>Books in English</i>				1.138	1.129	1.168	1.438
	<i>Other books</i>				1.011	1.002	1.015	1.020
	<i>Edited volumes</i>				1.175**	1.176**	1.158*	1.161*
	<i>Textbooks</i>				1.344+	1.390+	1.406+	1.436*
	Cumulative number of years of:	<i>ANR grants</i>					1.027	1.032
<i>ERC grants</i>						1.186	1.204	1.0801
<i>CNRS chair</i>						1.028	0.914	0.882
<i>Delegation CNRS, Labex, IUF</i>						0.916	0.884	0.881
<i>Admin: head of research center</i>							1.220***	1.230***
<i>Admin: head of department</i>							1.025	1.071
<i>1st AP-position in/around Paris</i>								1.791*
<i>Ever in secondment</i>							0.208*	
<i>Ever inactive</i>							0.785	

+ p<.10, * p<.05, ** p<.01, *** p<.001

All models: N=8175; Subjects=658; Failures=110

Significant difference: + $p < 0.1$, * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$

Data source: French Ministry of Higher Education and Research (MESRI), 2022.

Sample: Complete population of individuals who were recruited as assistant professors (“*maîtres de conférences*”) in sociology/demography (CNU section 19) at French universities between years 2000 and 2020, followed through 2021.

§flagship publications (alphabetical order): American Journal of Sociology, Annual Review of Sociology, American Sociological Review, Demography, Economie et Statistique, Espace Population et Société, European Sociological Review, Journal of Marriage and the Family, Population, Population and Development Review, Revue Française de Sociologie, Sociological Review, Sociologie du Travail, Sociologies, Sociology, Travail Genre Societé.

‡AERES lists 2008-2013.

Table 4: Cox regression on the hazard of becoming full professor (exponentiated coefficients: hazard ratios), by gender

		Men	Women	Sig. Dif.
	<i>Age at recruitment AP</i>	1.078**	1.074*	
Cumulative number of:	<i>Top articles[§]</i>	1.606*	1.610**	
	<i>Classified articles[£]</i>	1.238***	1.150*	
	<i>Other articles</i>	1.088*	0.938	+
	<i>Articles sole author</i>	0.912+	1.057	+
	<i>English articles</i>	0.932	1.133	+
	<i>Books sole author</i>	1.072	1.232	
	<i>Books in English</i>	0.588	4.764**	*
	<i>Other books</i>	0.946	1.289	
	<i>Edited volumes</i>	1.136+	1.359+	
	<i>Textbooks</i>	0.954	1.500**	
Cumulative number of years of:	<i>ANR grants</i>	1.160	0.938	
	<i>ERC grants</i>	1.114	1	
	<i>CNRS chair</i>	0.788	1	
	<i>Delegation CNRS, Labex, IUF</i>	0.529*	1.210	*
	<i>Admin: head of research center</i>	1.258***	1.178+	
	<i>Admin: head of department</i>	1.191	0.828	+
	<i>1st AP-position in/around Paris</i>	2.357*	1.627	
	<i>Ever in secondment</i>	0.203+	6.20e-20	
	<i>Ever inactive</i>	0.526	2.452	
	Year-fixed effects	yes	yes	
	N	3770	4405	
	Subjects	307	351	
	Failures	69	41	

Significant difference: + p<0.1, * p<0.05, ** p<0.01, *** p<0.001 (significance levels of two-sided tests of mean differences between men and women).

Data source: French Ministry of Higher Education and Research (MESRI), 2022.

Sample: Complete population of individuals who were recruited as assistant professors (“*maîtres de conférences*”) in sociology/demography (CNU section 19) at French universities between years 2000 and 2020, followed through 2021.

[§]flagship publications (alphabetical order): American Journal of Sociology, Annual Review of Sociology, American Sociological Review, Demography, Economie et Statistique, Espace Population et Société, European Sociological Review, Journal of Marriage and the Family, Population, Population and

Development Review, Revue Française de Sociologie, Sociological Review, Sociologie du Travail, Sociologies, Sociology, Travail Genre Société.

‡AERES lists 2008-2013.

Table 5: Cox regression on the hazard of applying for qualification (exponentiated coefficients: hazard ratios)

		1	2	3	
		Gender only	Time var. added	All control variables added	
Year-fixed effects		no	yes	yes	
Cumulative number of:	<i>Female</i>	0.550***	0.574***	0.716+	
	<i>Age at recruitment AP</i>		1.022	1.042*	
	<i>Top articles[§]</i>			1.329*	
	<i>Classified articles[£]</i>			1.115***	
	<i>Other articles</i>			1.010	
	<i>Articles sole author</i>			1.011	
	<i>English articles</i>			1.078+	
	<i>Books sole author</i>			1.267**	
	<i>Books in English</i>			1.003	
	<i>Other books</i>			1.121	
	<i>Edited volumes</i>			1.131+	
	<i>Textbooks</i>			1.400**	
	Cumulative number of years of:	<i>ANR grants</i>			1.078
		<i>ERC grants</i>			1.115
<i>CNRS chair</i>				0.871	
<i>Delegation CNRS, Labex, IUF</i>				0.998	
<i>Admin: head of research center</i>				1.239*	
<i>Admin: head of department</i>				0.947	
	<i>1st AP-position in/around Paris</i>			1.654*	
	<i>Ever in secondment</i>			0.399+	
	<i>Ever inactive</i>			1.155	

All models: N=7840; Subjects=658; Failures=156

Significant difference: + p<0.1, * p<0.05, ** p<0.01, *** p<0.001.

Data source: French Ministry of Higher Education and Research (MESRI), 2022.

Sample: Complete population of individuals who were recruited as assistant professors (“*maîtres de conférences*”) in sociology/demography (CNU section 19) at French universities between years 2000 and 2020, followed through 2021.

[§]flagship publications (alphabetical order): American Journal of Sociology, Annual Review of Sociology, American Sociological Review, Demography, Economie et Statistique, Espace Population et Société, European Sociological Review, Journal of Marriage and the Family, Population, Population and Development Review, Revue Française de Sociologie, Sociological Review, Sociologie du Travail, Sociologies, Sociology, Travail Genre Societé.

[£]AERES lists 2008-2013.

Table 6: Cox regression on the hazard of becoming qualified conditioned on application for qualification (exponentiated coefficients: hazard ratios)

		1	2	3
		Gender only	Time var. added	All control variables added
Year-fixed effects		no	yes	yes
	<i>Female</i>	0.915	0.875	0.887
	<i>Age at recruitment AP</i>		1.015	1.050*
Cumulative number of:	<i>Top articles[§]</i>			1.107
	<i>Classified articles[£]</i>			1.075**
	<i>Other articles</i>			0.953*
	<i>Articles sole author</i>			1.051+
	<i>English articles</i>			1.014
	<i>Books sole author</i>			1.164
	<i>Books in English</i>			0.953
	<i>Other books</i>			1.101*
	<i>Edited volumes</i>			1.277***
	<i>Textbooks</i>			1.396***
Cumulative number of years of:	<i>ANR grants</i>			0.944
	<i>ERC grants</i>			0.890
	<i>CNRS chair</i>			1.065
	<i>Delegation CNRS, Labex, IUF</i>			0.811*
	<i>Admin: head of research center</i>			0.948
	<i>Admin: head of department</i>			1.092+
	<i>1st AP-position in/around Paris</i>			1.637*
	<i>Ever in secondment</i>			0.443**
	<i>Ever inactive</i>			0.391**

All models: N=1931; Subjects=156; Failures=144

Significant difference: + p<0.1, * p<0.05, ** p<0.01, *** p<0.001.

Data source: French Ministry of Higher Education and Research (MESRI), 2022.

Sample: Complete population of individuals who were recruited as assistant professors (“*maîtres de conférences*”) in sociology/demography (CNU-section 19) at French universities between years 2000 and 2020 and who have applied for qualification for full professorship in CNU-section 19 until 2021.

§flagship publications (alphabetical order): American Journal of Sociology, Annual Review of Sociology, American Sociological Review, Demography, Economie et Statistique, Espace Population et Société, European Sociological Review, Journal of Marriage and the Family, Population, Population and Development Review, Revue Française de Sociologie, Sociological Review, Sociologie du Travail, Sociologies, Sociology, Travail Genre Societé.

€AERES lists 2008-2013.

Table 7: Cox regression on the hazard of applying for full professorship conditioned on being qualified (exponentiated coefficients: hazard ratios)

		1	2	3
		Gender only	Time var. added	All control variables added
Year-fixed effects		no	yes	yes
	<i>Female</i>	0.852	0.829	0.807
	<i>Age at recruitment AP</i>		1.040**	1.060***
Cumulative number of:	<i>Top articles[§]</i>			1.047
	<i>Classified articles[£]</i>			1.021
	<i>Other articles</i>			0.957
	<i>Articles sole author</i>			1.066*
	<i>English articles</i>			1.172*
	<i>Books sole author</i>			1.086
	<i>Books in English</i>			1.171
	<i>Other books</i>			1.061
	<i>Edited volumes</i>			1.226***
	<i>Textbooks</i>			1.432***
Cumulative number of years of:	<i>ANR grants</i>			0.829*
	<i>ERC grants</i>			0.880
	<i>CNRS chair</i>			1.260+
	<i>Delegation CNRS, Labex, IUF</i>			0.764*
	<i>Admin: head of research center</i>			0.959
	<i>Admin: head of department</i>			0.905
	<i>1st AP-position in/around Paris</i>			1.459
	<i>Ever in secondment</i>			0.398*
	<i>Ever inactive</i>			0.362**

All models: N=1830; Subjects=144; Failures=135

Significant difference: + p<0.1, * p<0.05, ** p<0.01, *** p<0.001.

Data source: French Ministry of Higher Education and Research (MESRI), 2022.

Sample: Complete population of individuals who were recruited as assistant professors (“*maîtres de conférences*”) in sociology/demography (CNU section 19) at French universities between years 2000 and 2020 and who became qualified for full professorship in CNU section 19 until 2021.

[§]flagship publications (alphabetical order): American Journal of Sociology, Annual Review of Sociology, American Sociological Review, Demography, Economie et Statistique, Espace Population et Société, European Sociological Review, Journal of Marriage and the Family, Population, Population and Development Review, Revue Française de Sociologie, Sociological Review, Sociologie du Travail, Sociologies, Sociology, Travail Genre Societé.

[£]AERES lists 2008-2013.

Table 8: Cox regression on the hazard of becoming full professor conditioned on applying for full professorship (exponentiated coefficients: hazard ratios)

		1	2	3	4	5
		Gender only	Time var. added	Usual control variables added	Nb. of applications added	Outside application added
Year-fixed effects		no	yes	yes	yes	yes
	<i>Female</i>	0.816	0.814	0.647+	0.651+	0.699
	<i>Age at recruitment AP</i>		1.019	1.043+	1.039+	1.040+
Cumulative number of:	<i>Top articles[§]</i>			1.224	1.287+	1.277+
	<i>Classified articles[£]</i>			1.087*	1.097**	1.101**
	<i>Other articles</i>			1.017	1.058+	1.046
	<i>Articles sole author</i>			1.016	0.998	1.008
	<i>English articles</i>			0.936	0.881	0.874
	<i>Books sole author</i>			0.822	0.739*	0.741*
	<i>Books in English</i>			1.279	1.380	1.501
	<i>Other books</i>			0.974	0.932	0.943
	<i>Edited volumes</i>			1.098	1.134+	1.119
	<i>Textbooks</i>			1.292*	1.260+	1.296*
Cumulative number of years of:	<i>ANR grants</i>			0.766	0.810	0.771
	<i>ERC grants</i>			1.153	1.154	1.154
	<i>CNRS chair</i>			1.027	0.988	1.021
	<i>Delegation CNRS, Labex, IUF</i>			0.791	0.858	0.833
	<i>Admin: head of research center</i>			1.144	1.180+	1.143
	<i>Admin: head of department</i>			0.941	0.837	0.823
	<i>1st AP-position in/around Paris</i>			1.831*	1.879**	2.049**

<i>Ever in secondment</i>	0.238*	0.330	0.360
<i>Ever inactive</i>	0.349	0.404	0.400
<i>Cumulative number of applications</i>		1.104**	1.109**
<i>Ever outside application</i>			0.571*

All models: N=1871; Subjects=135; Failures=98

Significant difference: + p<0.1, * p<0.05, ** p<0.01, *** p<0.001.

Data source: French Ministry of Higher Education and Research (MESRI), 2022.

Sample: Complete population of individuals who were recruited as assistant professors (*“maîtres de conférences”*) in sociology/demography (CNU section 19) at French universities between years 2000 and 2020 and who became qualified for full professorship in CNU section 19 until 2021.

§flagship publications (alphabetical order): American Journal of Sociology, Annual Review of Sociology, American Sociological Review, Demography, Economie et Statistique, Espace Population et Société, European Sociological Review, Journal of Marriage and the Family, Population, Population and Development Review, Revue Française de Sociologie, Sociological Review, Sociologie du Travail, Sociologies, Sociology, Travail Genre Societé.

‡AERES lists 2008-2013.

Table 9: Cox regression on the hazard of becoming full professor conditioned on applying for full professorship (exponentiated coefficients: hazard ratios): internal vs external recruitment

		Internal recruitment		External recruitment	
		1	2	3	4
		Gender only	With control variables	Gender only	With control variables
Cumulative number of:	<i>Female</i>	1.074	1.191	0.662	0.482+
	<i>Age at recruitment AP</i>		0.984		1.076*
	<i>Top articles[§]</i>		1.025		1.480+
	<i>Classified articles[£]</i>		1.034		1.141**
	<i>Other articles</i>		1.016		1.062
	<i>Articles sole author</i>		1.044		0.984
	<i>English articles</i>		1.032		0.696
	<i>Books sole author</i>		0.816		0.702*
	<i>Books in English</i>		2.126		0.947
	<i>Other books</i>		0.997		0.929
	<i>Edited volumes</i>		0.901		1.241*
	<i>Textbooks</i>		1.432*		1.021
	Cumulative number of years of:	<i>ANR grants</i>		0.628	
<i>ERC grants</i>			5.59e-10		1.470
<i>CNRS chair</i>			6.12e-10		0.964
<i>Delegation CNRS, Labex, IUF</i>			0.842		0.752
<i>Admin: head of research center</i>			1.158		1.227
<i>Admin: head of department</i>			0.902		0.761
<i>1st AP-position in/around Paris</i>			1.864+		2.232*
<i>Ever in secondment</i>			0.449		0.383
<i>Ever inactive</i>			4.20e-20***		1.056
<i>Cumulative number of applications</i>			1.084+		1.136**
<i>Ever outside application</i>		0.208***		1.490	
Year-fixed effects	no	yes	no	yes	
N	1871	1871	1871	1871	
Subjects	135	135	135	135	
Failures	44	44	54	54	

Significant difference: + p<0.1, * p<0.05, ** p<0.01, *** p<0.001.

Data source: French Ministry of Higher Education and Research (MESRI), 2022.

Sample: Complete population of individuals who were recruited as assistant professors (“*maîtres de conférences*”) in sociology/demography (CNU section 19) at French universities between years 2000 and 2020 and who became qualified for full professorship in CNU section 19 until 2021.

§flagship publications (alphabetical order): American Journal of Sociology, Annual Review of Sociology, American Sociological Review, Demography, Economie et Statistique, Espace Population et Société, European Sociological Review, Journal of Marriage and the Family, Population, Population and Development Review, Revue Française de Sociologie, Sociological Review, Sociologie du Travail, Sociologies, Sociology, Travail Genre Societé.

‡AERES lists 2008-2013.

Appendix

Figure A: Proportion of women amongst AP and FP (left panel) and proportion of full professors by sex (right panel) in sociology/demography in France, 1985 to 2020

Data source: French Ministry of Higher Education and Research (MESRI), 2022.

Sample: Complete population of assistant professors (*“maîtres de conférences”*) and full professors in sociology/demography (CNU section 19) at French universities between years 1985 and 2020, cross-sectional sample.

Figure B: Average number of articles and books published at year of recruitment as assistant professor, by sex

Data source: French Ministry of Higher Education and Research (MESRI), 2022; publication records based on own compilations

Sample: Complete population of individuals who were recruited as assistant professors (“*maîtres de conférences*”) in sociology/demography (CNU section 19) at French universities between years 2000 and 2020, followed through 2021.

Figure C: Average cumulated number of scientific production at years since recruitment as assistant professor, by sex

OLS-regressions with cohort fixed-effects and robust, panel-corrected standard errors clustered by person

Data source: French Ministry of Higher Education and Research (MESRI), 2022; publication records based on own compilations

Sample: Complete population of individuals who were recruited as assistant professors (“*maîtres de conférences*”) in sociology/demography (CNU section 19) at French universities between years 2000 and 2020, followed through 2021.

[§]flagship publications (alphabetical order): American Journal of Sociology, Annual Review of Sociology, American Sociological Review, Demography, Economie et Statistique, Espace Population et Société, European Sociological Review, Journal of Marriage and the Family, Population, Population and Development Review, Revue Française de Sociologie, Sociological Review, Sociologie du Travail, Sociologies, Sociology, Travail Genre Societé.

[‡]AERES lists 2008-2013.

Figure D: Average number of applications of men and women for assistant professor and full professor positions in sociology/demography in France, by calendar year

Average number of applications

Data source: French Ministry of Higher Education and Research (MESRI), 2025.

Note: numbers not available for year 2012

Figure E.1: Assistant professors: The proportion of women, odds, odds ratio amongst candidates and odds ratio amongst applications at recruitment, by calendar year.

Data source: French Ministry of Higher Education and Research (MESRI), 2025.

Note: numbers not available for year 2012

Figure E.2: Full professors: The proportion of women, odds, odds ratio amongst candidates and odds ratio amongst applications at recruitment, by calendar year.

Data source: French Ministry of Higher Education and Research (MESRI), 2025.

Note: numbers not available for year 2012

Table A: Illustration of data structure – simplified example

id	cohort	year	nb publications	nb cum publications	PU
1	2000	1999	4	4	0
1	2000	2000	1	5	0
1	2000	2001	0	5	0
1	2000	2002	3	8	0
1	2000	2003	2	10	0
1	2000	2004	0	10	1
1	2000	2005	1	11	1
		1
1	2000	2021	0	20	1
2	2010	2009	5	5	0
2	2010	2010	2	7	0
2	2010	2011	3	10	0
2	2010	2012	1	11	0
2	2010	2013	2	13	0
...	0
2	2010	2021	1	16	0

Source: authors' own compilation

Table A reads as follows:

Individual 1 is recruited as assistant professor in the year 2000 and is observed continuously until year 2021 in the MESRI-database. The cumulated number of publications until the calendar year prior to the recruitment as assistant professor (year 1999) amounts to four. Individual 1 published one publication during the year of recruitment (year 2000), zero in year 2001, three in year 2002 and so forth. Individual 1 became a full professor in calendar year 2004. The cumulated publications amount to 10 in year 2004. Due to the transition to full professor in year 2004, the person-years observed for calendar years 2005+ are not considered by the Cox model.

Individual 2 is recruited as assistant professor in the year 2010 and is observed continuously until year 2021 in the MESRI-database. The cumulated number of publications until the calendar year prior to the recruitment as assistant professor (year 2009) amounts to five. Individual 2 published two publications during the year of recruitment (year 2010), three in year 2011, one in year 2012 and so forth. Individual 2 did not transition to full professor until 2021. The cumulated publications amount to 16 in year 2021.

Table B: Characteristics of sociologists who became assistant professor at French universities (observed at year of recruitment)

	<i>Men</i>		<i>Women</i>		<i>Sig. Dif.</i>
	<i>Mean</i>	<i>(st. dev.)</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>(st. dev.)</i>	
<i>Age at recruitment as AP</i>	35,71	(0,32)	35,09	(0,28)	-
<u>Cumulative number of:</u>					
<i>Articles (total)</i>	4,31	(0,23)	3,99	(0,19)	-
<i>Top articles[§]</i>	0,19	(0,02)	0,19	(0,02)	-
<i>Classified articles[‡]</i>	1,95	(0,12)	2,01	(0,11)	-
<i>Other articles</i>	2,36	(0,17)	1,98	(0,13)	-
<i>Articles sole author</i>	3,12	(0,17)	2,84	(0,15)	-
<i>English articles</i>	0,23	(0,04)	0,25	(0,05)	-
<i>Books (total)</i>	0,57	(0,07)	0,43	(0,04)	-
<i>Books sole author</i>	0,36	(0,04)	0,25	(0,03)	*
<i>Books in English</i>	0,01	(0,01)	0,01	(0,00)	-
<i>Edited volumes</i>	0,13	(0,04)	0,13	(0,02)	-
<i>Textbooks</i>	0,02	(0,01)	0,01	(0,01)	-
<u>Dummy (0/1):</u>					
<i>1st AP-position in/around Paris</i>	0,19	(0,02)	0,23	(0,02)	-
Number of individuals	307		351		

Significant difference: + $p < 0.1$, * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$ (significance levels of two-sided tests of mean differences between men and women).

Data source: French Ministry of Higher Education and Research (MESRI), 2022.

Sample: Complete population of individuals who were recruited as assistant professors (“*maîtres de conférences*”) in sociology/demography (CNU section 19) at French universities between years 2000 and 2020, followed through 2021.

[§]flagship publications (alphabetical order): American Journal of Sociology, Annual Review of Sociology, American Sociological Review, Demography, Economie et Statistique, Espace Population et Société, European Sociological Review, Journal of Marriage and the Family, Population, Population and Development Review, Revue Française de Sociologie, Sociological Review, Sociologie du Travail, Sociologies, Sociology, Travail Genre Societé.

[‡]AERES lists 2008-2013.

Table C: Distribution over categories combining university affiliation at 1st recruitment as assistant professor (AP) and at 1st recruitment as full professor, by sex

	Men	Women	Total
AP in Paris and no university change	6	6	12
AP in Paris and university change within Paris	2	5	7
AP in Paris and university change out of Paris	9	1	10
AP outside Paris and no university change	25	14	39
AP outside Paris and university change to Paris	5	4	9
AP outside Paris and university change outside Paris	22	11	33
Total	69	41	110

Data source: French Ministry of Higher Education and Research (MESRI), 2022.

Sample: Complete population of individuals who were recruited as assistant professors (“*maîtres de conférences*”) in sociology/demography (CNU section 19) at French universities between years 2000 and 2020 and who became full professors until 2021.

Table D: Mlogit regression on the unconditioned probability of becoming full professor (FP) / of exiting the academic sector (exponentiated coefficients: odds ratios)

		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
		Gender only	Time var. added	Productivity (quant.) added	Productivity (qual.) added	Awards added	Admin. resp. added	1st AP in Paris added	Secondment/inactivity added
	Control for years and years ²	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes
Becoming FP									
	<i>Female</i>	0.476***	0.472***	0.576**	0.571*	0.581*	0.611*	0.595*	0.547**
	<i>Age at recruitment AP</i>		0.995	1.009	1.020	1.019	1.023	1.026	1.021
Cumulative number of:	<i>Articles</i>			1.054***					
	<i>Books</i>			1.169***					
	<i>Top articles^S</i>				1.340*	1.327*	1.329*	1.365*	1.369*
	<i>Classified articles^E</i>				1.115***	1.110***	1.113***	1.107**	1.117***
	<i>Articles sole author</i>				1.012	1.013	1.022	1.023	1.024
	<i>English articles</i>				0.963	0.963	0.972	0.978	1.004
	<i>Other articles</i>				1.021	1.020	1.006	1.004	0.997
	<i>Books sole author</i>				1.131	1.124	1.101	1.094	1.068
	<i>Books in English</i>				1.076	1.082	1.125	1.168	1.335
	<i>Other books</i>				1.046	1.053	1.061	1.064	1.075
Cumulative number of years of:	<i>Edited volumes</i>				1.185*	1.182*	1.162*	1.162*	1.166*
	<i>Textbooks</i>				1.360	1.339	1.365*	1.378*	1.379*
	<i>ANR grants</i>					1.006	1.019	1.004	0.980
	<i>ERC grants</i>					1.247	1.267	1.226	1.179
	<i>CNRS chair</i>					1.157	0.996	1.004	0.959
	<i>Delegation CNRS, Labex, IUF</i>					1.058	1.015	1.030	0.999
	<i>Admin: head of research center</i>						1.300***	1.316***	1.315***
	<i>Admin: head of department</i>						1.074	1.084	1.092
	<i>1st AP-position in/around Paris</i>							1.525+	1.561+
	<i>Ever in secondment</i>								0.176*
<i>Ever inactive</i>								0.993	

		Exit							
	<i>Female</i>	0.834	1.426	1.264	1.289	1.213	1.248	1.264	1.611
	<i>Age at recruitment AP</i>		1.263***	1.265***	1.268***	1.265***	1.261***	1.263***	1.304***
Cumulative number of:	<i>Articles</i>			1.030					
	<i>Books</i>			0.723*					
	<i>Top articles^S</i>				1.487***	1.443**	1.420**	1.409**	1.499**
	<i>Classified articles^E</i>				0.989	0.998	0.996	0.996	0.983
	<i>Articles sole author</i>				1.040	1.035	1.031	1.033	1.008
	<i>English articles</i>				1.119	1.112	1.117	1.118	1.129
	<i>Other articles</i>				0.974	0.979	0.974	0.973	0.972
	<i>Books sole author</i>				0.761	0.827	0.799	0.799	0.780
	<i>Books in English</i>				0.00000253***	0.00000146***	0.000000697***	0.000000362***	0.000000187***
	<i>Other books</i>				0.832	0.788	0.809	0.805	0.811
	<i>Edited volumes</i>				0.973	0.983	0.985	0.981	0.980
	<i>Textbooks</i>				0.00000451***	0.00000273***	0.000000943***	0.000000523***	0.00000104***
Cumulative number of years of:	<i>ANR grants</i>					1.152	1.116	1.113	1.097
	<i>ERC grants</i>					0.0000991***	0.0000345***	0.0000225***	0.0000825***
	<i>CNRS chair</i>					2.97e-09***	1.62e-09***	6.90e-10***	1.92e-09***
	<i>Delegation CNRS, Labex, IUF</i>					0.909	0.891	0.887	1.005
	<i>Admin: head of research center</i>						0.0000414***	0.0000282***	0.0000307***
	<i>Admin: head of department</i>						0.0000339***	0.0000186***	0.0000213***
	<i>1st AP-position in/around Paris</i>							0.903	0.889
	<i>Ever in secondment</i>								24.64***
	<i>Ever inactive</i>								15.12*

+ p<.10, * p<.05, ** p<.01, *** p<.001

All models: N=8732; Subjects=703; FailuresPU=110; FailuresExit=45

Std. err. adjusted for clusters

Significant difference: + p<0.1, * p<0.05, ** p<0.01, *** p<0.001.

Data source: French Ministry of Higher Education and Research (MESRI), 2022.

Sample: Complete population of individuals who were recruited as assistant professors (“*maîtres de conférences*”) in sociology/demography (CNU section 19) at French universities between years 2000 and 2020, followed through 2021.

[§]flagship publications (alphabetical order): American Journal of Sociology, Annual Review of Sociology, American Sociological Review, Demography, Economie et Statistique, Espace Population et Société, European Sociological Review, Journal of Marriage and the Family, Population, Population and Development Review, Revue Française de Sociologie, Sociological Review, Sociologie du Travail, Sociologies, Sociology, Travail Genre Societé.

[£]AERES lists 2008-2013.

Table E: Cox regression on the unconditioned hazard of becoming full professor (PU) (exponentiated coefficients: hazard ratios)

		Only FP in sociology/demography considered			FP in other disciplines: individuals entirely dropped		
		1	2	3	4	5	6
		Gender only	Time var. added	All control variables added	Gender only	Time var. added	All control variables added
Year-fixed effects		no	yes	yes	no	yes	yes
	<i>Female</i>	0.511**	0.529**	0.568*	0.503***	0.520**	0.564*
	<i>Age at recruitment AP</i>		1.009	1.062**		1.011	1.056*
Cumulative number of:	<i>Top articles^S</i>			1.619***			1.597***
	<i>Classified articles^E</i>			1.174***			1.169***
	<i>Other articles</i>			1.048			1.040
	<i>Articles sole author</i>			0.984			0.988
	<i>English articles</i>			0.970			0.975
	<i>Books sole author</i>			1.057			1.069
	<i>Books in English</i>			1.342			1.351
	<i>Other books</i>			1.007			1.006
	<i>Edited volumes</i>			1.140+			1.151*
	<i>Textbooks</i>			1.465*			1.461*
Cumulative number of years of:	<i>ANR grants</i>			0.965			0.965
	<i>ERC grants</i>			1.138			1.129
	<i>CNRS chair</i>			0.885			0.821
	<i>Delegation CNRS, Labex, IUF</i>			0.919			0.884
	<i>Admin: head of research center</i>			1.158+			1.333**
	<i>Admin: head of department</i>			1.042			1.024
	<i>1st AP-position in/around Paris</i>			2.001**			1.990**
<i>Ever in secondment</i>			0.245+			0.241+	
<i>Ever inactive</i>			0.621			0.795	
	N	8175	8175	8175	8049	8049	8049
	Subjects	658	658	658	646	646	646
	Failures	98	98	98	98	98	98

+ p<.10, * p<.05, ** p<.01, *** p<.001

Significant difference: + $p < 0.1$, * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$.

Data source: French Ministry of Higher Education and Research (MESRI), 2022.

Sample: Complete population of individuals who were recruited as assistant professors (“*maîtres de conférences*”) in sociology/demography (CNU section 19) at French universities between years 2000 and 2020, followed through 2021.

[§]flagship publications (alphabetical order): American Journal of Sociology, Annual Review of Sociology, American Sociological Review, Demography, Economie et Statistique, Espace Population et Société, European Sociological Review, Journal of Marriage and the Family, Population, Population and Development Review, Revue Française de Sociologie, Sociological Review, Sociologie du Travail, Sociologies, Sociology, Travail Genre Societé.

[£]AERES lists 2008-2013.

Table F: Cox regression on the hazard of applying for qualification (exponentiated coefficients: hazard ratios), by gender

		Men	Women	Sig. Dif.
	<i>Age at recruitment AP</i>	1.063*	1.041	
Cumulative number of:	<i>Top articles[§]</i>	1.197	1.410**	
	<i>Classified articles[£]</i>	1.151***	1.106*	
	<i>Other articles</i>	1.025	0.997	
	<i>Articles sole author</i>	0.977	1.039	
	<i>English articles</i>	1.044	1.228*	
	<i>Books sole author</i>	1.241+	1.384+	
	<i>Books in English</i>	0.757	1.247	
	<i>Other books</i>	1.111	1.089	
	<i>Edited volumes</i>	1.076	1.249	
	<i>Textbooks</i>	1.190	1.346*	
Cumulative number of years of:	<i>ANR grants</i>	1.107	1.115	
	<i>ERC grants</i>	1.077	1	
	<i>CNRS chair</i>	0.766	1	
	<i>Delegation CNRS, Labex, IUF</i>	0.723+	1.327+	*
	<i>Admin: head of research center</i>	1.493***	1.174+	+
	<i>Admin: head of department</i>	0.905	0.899	
	<i>1st AP-position in/around Paris</i>	1.841+	1.605+	
	<i>Ever in secondment</i>	0.518	2.97e-20	***
	<i>Ever inactive</i>	0.800	1.502	
	Year-fixed effects	yes	yes	
	N	3568	4272	
	Subjects	307	351	
	Failures	91	65	

+ p<.10, * p<.05, ** p<.01, *** p<.001

Significant difference: + p<0.1, * p<0.05, ** p<0.01, *** p<0.001 (significance levels of two-sided tests of mean differences between men and women).

Data source: French Ministry of Higher Education and Research (MESRI), 2022.

Sample: Complete population of individuals who were recruited as assistant professors (“*maîtres de conférences*”) in sociology/demography (CNU section 19) at French universities between years 2000 and 2020, followed through 2021.

[§]flagship publications (alphabetical order): American Journal of Sociology, Annual Review of Sociology, American Sociological Review, Demography, Economie et Statistique, Espace Population et Société, European Sociological Review, Journal of Marriage and the Family, Population, Population and

Development Review, Revue Française de Sociologie, Sociological Review, Sociologie du Travail, Sociologies, Sociology, Travail Genre Société.

‡AERES lists 2008-2013.

Table G: Cox regression on the hazard of becoming qualified conditioned on applying for qualification (exponentiated coefficients: hazard ratios), by gender

		Men	Women	Sig. Dif.
Cumulative number of:	<i>Age at recruitment AP</i>	1.015	1.109**	+
	<i>Top articles[§]</i>	1.004	1.153	
	<i>Classified articles[£]</i>	1.075+	1.160***	
	<i>Other articles</i>	0.951	0.966	
	<i>Articles sole author</i>	1.044	1.073+	
	<i>English articles</i>	0.977	1.032	
	<i>Books sole author</i>	1.198	1.181	
	<i>Books in English</i>	0.739	2.007	+
	<i>Other books</i>	0.946	1.084	
	<i>Edited volumes</i>	1.334***	1.104	
	<i>Textbooks</i>	2.362***	1.214+	*
	Cumulative number of years of:	<i>ANR grants</i>	0.919	0.957
<i>ERC grants</i>		0.930	1	
<i>CNRS chair</i>		1.085	1	
<i>Delegation CNRS, Labex, IUF</i>		0.649***	1.115	**
<i>Admin: head of research center</i>		0.908	0.911	
<i>Admin: head of department</i>		1.130	1.219	
<i>1st AP-position in/around Paris</i>		1.571	1.206	
<i>Ever in secondment</i>	0.235**	/		
<i>Ever inactive</i>	0.161***	0.690		
	Year-fixed effects	yes	yes	
	N	1112	819	
	Subjects	91	65	
	Failures	82	62	

+ p<.10, * p<.05, ** p<.01, *** p<.001

Significant difference: + p<0.1, * p<0.05, ** p<0.01, *** p<0.001 (significance levels of two-sided tests of mean differences between men and women).

Data source: French Ministry of Higher Education and Research (MESRI), 2022.

Sample: Complete population of individuals who were recruited as assistant professors (“*maîtres de conférences*”) in sociology/demography (CNU-section 19) at French universities between years 2000 and 2020 and who have applied for qualification for full professorship in CNU-section 19 until 2021.

[§]flagship publications (alphabetical order): American Journal of Sociology, Annual Review of Sociology, American Sociological Review, Demography, Economie et Statistique, Espace Population et Société, European Sociological Review, Journal of Marriage and the Family, Population, Population and

Development Review, Revue Française de Sociologie, Sociological Review, Sociologie du Travail, Sociologies, Sociology, Travail Genre Société.

‡AERES lists 2008-2013.

Table H: Cox regression on the hazard of applying for full professorship conditioned on being qualified (exponentiated coefficients: hazard ratios), by gender

		Men	Women	Sig. Dif.
	<i>Age at recruitment AP</i>	1.033	1.135**	*
Cumulative number of:	<i>Top articles[§]</i>	1.240	0.894	
	<i>Classified articles[£]</i>	1.033	1.115**	
	<i>Other articles</i>	0.955	0.916*	
	<i>Articles sole author</i>	1.065	1.114*	
	<i>English articles</i>	1.070	1.323*	
	<i>Books sole author</i>	0.922	1.607*	+
	<i>Books in English</i>	0.803	2.237	
	<i>Other books</i>	0.878	1.132	*
	<i>Edited volumes</i>	1.282***	0.977	
	<i>Textbooks</i>	2.786***	1.232*	***
Cumulative number of years of:	<i>ANR grants</i>	0.750	0.846	
	<i>ERC grants</i>	0.992	1	
	<i>CNRS chair</i>	0.994	1	
	<i>Delegation CNRS, Labex, IUF</i>	0.492**	1.077	*
	<i>Admin: head of research center</i>	1.104	0.772	+
	<i>Admin: head of department</i>	1.019	0.774	
	<i>1st AP-position in/around Paris</i>	1.970*	0.931	
	<i>Ever in secondment</i>	0.248***	/	
	<i>Ever inactive</i>	0.214***	0.194	
	Year-fixed effects	yes	yes	
	N	1034	796	
	Subjects	82	62	
	Failures	78	57	

+ p<.10, * p<.05, ** p<.01, *** p<.001

Significant difference: + p<0.1, * p<0.05, ** p<0.01, *** p<0.001 (significance levels of two-sided tests of mean differences between men and women).

Data source: French Ministry of Higher Education and Research (MESRI), 2022.

Sample: Complete population of individuals who were recruited as assistant professors (“*maîtres de conférences*”) in sociology/demography (CNU section 19) at French universities between years 2000 and 2020 and who became qualified for full professorship in CNU section 19 until 2021.

[§]flagship publications (alphabetical order): American Journal of Sociology, Annual Review of Sociology, American Sociological Review, Demography, Economie et Statistique, Espace Population et Société, European Sociological Review, Journal of Marriage and the Family, Population, Population and

Development Review, Revue Française de Sociologie, Sociological Review, Sociologie du Travail, Sociologies, Sociology, Travail Genre Société.

‡AERES lists 2008-2013.

Table I: Cox regression on the hazard of becoming full professor conditioned on applying for full professorship (exponentiated coefficients: hazard ratios), by gender

		Men	Women	Sig. Dif.
	<i>Age at recruitment AP</i>	1.038	1.212**	*
Cumulative number of:	<i>Top articles[§]</i>	1.418+	1.515	
	<i>Classified articles[£]</i>	1.170**	1.096	
	<i>Other articles</i>	1.086	1.024	
	<i>Articles sole author</i>	0.930	1.150+	*
	<i>English articles</i>	0.951	0.676*	
	<i>Books sole author</i>	0.699+	0.801	
	<i>Books in English</i>	1.79e-18	9.225***	
	<i>Other books</i>	0.762***	0.963	
	<i>Edited volumes</i>	1.324***	0.561*	**
	<i>Textbooks</i>	1.381	1.644*	
Cumulative number of years of:	<i>ANR grants</i>	1.766*	0.577*	**
	<i>ERC grants</i>	1.089	1	
	<i>CNRS chair</i>	0.987	1	
	<i>Délégation CNRS, Labex, IUF</i>	0.535	0.918	
	<i>Admin: head of research center</i>	0.944	0.843	
	<i>Admin: head of department</i>	0.942	1.071	
	<i>1st AP-position in/around Paris</i>	2.114*	4.477*	
	<i>Ever in secondment</i>	0.223*	/	
	<i>Ever inactive</i>	0.0431***	0.715	
	<i>Cumulative number of applications</i>	1.090+	1.158*	
	<i>Ever outside application</i>	0.651	0.381*	
	Year-fixed effects	yes	yes	
	N	1082	789	
	Subjects	78	57	
	Failures	60	38	

+ p<.10, * p<.05, ** p<.01, *** p<.001

Significant difference: + p<0.1, * p<0.05, ** p<0.01, *** p<0.001 (significance levels of two-sided tests of mean differences between men and women).

Data source: French Ministry of Higher Education and Research (MESRI), 2022.

Sample: Complete population of individuals who were recruited as assistant professors (“*maîtres de conférences*”) in sociology/demography (CNU section 19) at French universities between years 2000 and 2020 and who became qualified for full professorship in CNU section 19 until 2021.

[§]flagship publications (alphabetical order): American Journal of Sociology, Annual Review of Sociology, American Sociological Review, Demography, Economie et Statistique, Espace Population et Société, European Sociological Review, Journal of Marriage and the Family, Population, Population and Development Review, Revue Française de Sociologie, Sociological Review, Sociologie du Travail, Sociologies, Sociology, Travail Genre Societé.

[£]AERES lists 2008-2013.

Table J: Decomposition analysis

	Predicted promotion rate men	Predicted promotion rate women	Gender gap in promotion (%)	Cumulative contribution (%)	Contribution to the overall gender gap in promotion (%)
Applying for qualification	55.6	37.73	32.21	74.30	74.30
Becoming qualified	54.04	36.50	32.46	74.87	0.60
Applying for full professorship	51.52	34.00	34.01	78.44	3.60
Becoming full professor	39.95	22.63	43.35	100.00	21.56

Data source: French Ministry of Higher Education and Research (MESRI), 2022.

Sample: Complete population of individuals who were recruited as assistant professors (*“maîtres de conférences”*) in sociology/demography (CNU section 19) at French universities between years 2000 and 2020, followed through 2021.

Columns 1 and 2 - Predicted promotion rate for men and women: Numbers based on cox proportional hazard regressions with sex as only independent variable: 1-survival rate as assistant professor observed 20 years after first recruitment as assistant professor.

Column, 3 - Gender gap in promotion: $1 - (\text{predicted promotion rate women} / \text{predicted promotion rate men})$

Column 4 - Cumulative contribution: The overall gender gap in becoming full professor of 43,35% (4th line in 3rd column) is set at 100%: Accordingly, the gender gap in applying for qualification represents 74,30% of the overall gender gap. The cumulative gender gaps in applying for qualification and becoming qualified represent 74,87% of the overall gender gap. The cumulative gender gaps in applying for qualification, becoming qualified and applying for full professorship represent 78,44% of the overall gender gap.

Column 5: Contribution to the overall gender gap in promotion: Difference between the cumulative contribution of the latter cumulative contribution and the previous cumulative contribution.